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to increase the development
and adoption of IPM tools

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IPM Packages report

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Table of content

1. Public summary	3
2. Introduction	3
3. IPM Packages	4
TOMATO.....	4
Examples of IPM Packages on tomato.....	19
LETTUCE.....	21
Examples of IPM Packages on lettuce	25
CABBAGE.....	26
WHEAT	30
Examples of IPM Packages on wheat.....	36
MAIZE	37
Examples of IPM Packages on maize.....	40
4. Conclusion	41
5. References.....	41

1. Public summary

The IPM Packages were designed in the ADOPT-IPM project to collect all IPM solutions that can be used in the countries involved in the project. A list of current practices already in use was compiled to provide a current overview of IPM. To this was added the list of innovative solutions developed in the project through the activities carried out in WP1 and WP2. The list is continuously being updated and as of this year, these solutions have been applied in the field trials planned for WP4. The field applications represent the output of this work and in this document, after presenting the IPM packages, some examples of field applications adopted by the project partners are given.

2. Introduction

The IPM package is a set of solutions applicable to integrated crop production (IPM). The basic concept is to manage the various pests affecting the crop (pathogens, insects and weeds) by applying IPM, including low-impact solutions such as agronomic, physical and biological methods and tools.

At present, the solutions available in some of the ADOPT-IPM project countries are included. The project partners have updated them, indicating whether the current solutions are also available in their country and adding other standard solutions if available. The crops considered in the project are tomato, wheat, maize and leafy vegetables (lettuce and cabbage), and an IPM package is available for each crop.

The IPM package is currently an Excel file that consists of a list of management solutions divided into categories: 'Agronomic tools', 'Genetic tools', 'Monitoring', 'Physical tools', 'Biological tools', 'Chemical tools' and 'ADOPT-IPM solutions'. The ADOPT-IPM solutions, developed in WP1 and WP2, have been included, after the ADOPT-IPM technology models, with information on the tools developed in the research activities that have demonstrated effectiveness against a particular pest for the crops considered in the project, have been compiled by the partners.

Each sheet in the Excel file relates to a different pest affecting the crop under examination (e.g. powdery mildew in tomatoes). The table in each sheet lists the currently applicable solutions with some general details. An important part of the information, for example, is the 'Production Phase', i.e. the point in the crop production cycle at which a particular solution can be applied. To be more precise on this aspect, it is preferable to refer to the phenological stage of the crop as defined by the BBCH scale, a parameter that is usually found on the labels of some pesticides.

Additional notes and details can be added, such as product use concentrations and the maximum number of applications per year.

There is a 'Country' section covering all countries involved in the ADOPT-IPM project, where all solutions that can be used in integrated agriculture (IPM) are marked. Each partner has filled in the 'Country' column by adding an 'x' in the cell next to the solution already written in case the solution is available in your country. Or added a new row in the Excel file to include other applicable solutions in the package.

In this way it was possible to obtain a complete list of all IPM solutions that can be implemented in each country involved in the ADOPT project, both the current ones and those developed during the project. The IPM packages will in fact be updated annually as new innovative solutions are developed during the project.

3. IPM Packages

TOMATO: *The tomato IPM package is shown on the following pages. Each sheet is related to a different pest (pathogen, insect, weed), with the corresponding management solutions.*

Powdery mildew (*Pseudoidium neolycopersici*, *Erysiphe* spp., *Leveillula taurica*)

Crop	Insect pests and diseases	Management solutions	Country					Solution/Practice/Active Ingredient	Product category	Chemical group	Production stage (if possible with reference to BBCH scale)	Max number of application per year	Application Details and Notes (commercial product example)	Resistance risk (FRAC Code)		
			IT	FR	ES	BE	NL								DK	CN
Tomato	Powdery mildew (<i>Pseudoidium neolycopersici</i> , <i>Erysiphe</i> spp., <i>Leveillula taurica</i>)	Agronomic tools	x	x				Plant in sunny areas as much as possible			Sowing/Planting					
			x	x				Provide good air circulation.			From Sowing/Planting to Harvest					
			x	x				Avoid applying excess fertilizer.			From Sowing/Planting to Harvest					
			x	x				Overhead sprinkling may help reduce powdery mildew			From Sowing/Planting to Harvest					
			x	x				Calcium fertilizer treatments			From Sowing/Planting to Harvest					
		Genetic Tools	x	x				Resistant varieties are available (for example LANCASTER, LUTECIA and ORINADE -Gautier semeces-)			Sowing/Planting					
			Monitoring	x	x				Observations on plants are needed: threshold 3% disease severity.			From Sowing/Planting to Harvest				
						x			Observation: presence/absence							
					x				Prediction models are not available.							
		Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)	x	x					<i>Ampelomyces quisqualis</i> M-10	Microbiological fungicide		from BBCH 10 to BBCH 89	12	(AQ-10) Contact organic fungicide. Dosage: 35-70 g/ha. Keep the suspension in agitation during the application		
			x	x					<i>Bacillus omyloquifaciens</i> - FZB24	Microbiological fungicide		from BBCH 10 to BBCH 89	12	(Taegro) Contact organic fungicide. Dosage: 3 Kg/ha		
			x	x					<i>Bacillus omyloquifaciens plantarum</i> - D747	Microbiological fungicide		from the appearance of the first symptoms to BBCH 89	6	(Amylo-X) Dosage: 1.5-2.5 Kg/ha		
			x	x					<i>Bacillus pumilus</i> - QST 2808	Microbiological fungicide		from BBCH 10 to BBCH 89	6	(Sonata) Contact organic fungicide. Dosage: 5-10 L/ha		
			x	x					POTASSIUM BICARBONATE	Biological fungicide	Basic substance	from BBCH 10 to BBCH 89	6	(KARMA 85) Contact organic fungicide. Dosage: 5-10 L/ha.		
			x	x					COS - OGA	Biological fungicide	low risk Active substance	from BBCH 13 to BBCH 89	5	(IBISCO) Dosage: 2 L/ha		
			x	x					sweet orange essential oil	Biological fungicide						
			x	x					EUGENOL	Biological fungicide	Natural compound	from BBCH 42 to BBCH 89	5	(3LOGY) Fungicide based on terpenes that acts by contact, with activity preventive control. Dosage: 2-3 L/ha		
			x	x					GERANIOL	Biological fungicide	Natural compound	from BBCH 42 to BBCH 89	5	(3LOGY) Fungicide based on terpenes that acts by contact, with activity preventive control. Dosage: 2-3 L/ha		
			x	x					THYMOL	Biological fungicide	Natural compound	from BBCH 42 to BBCH 89	5	(3LOGY) Fungicide based on terpenes that acts by contact, with activity preventive control. Dosage: 2-3 L/ha		
			x	x					Sulfur	Inorganic fungicide	Inorganic	from BBCH 10 to BBCH 89	6	(Triovit Jet) Dosage 1.5-5 Kg/ha. Triovit Jet is not compatible with alkaline insecticides and mineral oils.		
			Chemical tools	x	x					Boscalid	Synthetic fungicide	SDHI (Succinate dehydrogenase inhibitors)	when first symptoms occur	3 (Among Boscalid, Fluopyram, Pentoxiprad, Fluxapyroxad, Isopyrazam)	(BAS 5101 F) Contact fungicide with translinar properties. Dosage 0.2 Kg/ha	Medium to high risk (7)
				x	x	x				Cyflufenamid	Synthetic fungicide	phenylacetamide	when first symptoms occur. Suspend treatments 1 day before harvest	2	(TAKUM) Dosage: 150ml/ha	Resistance in Sphaerotheca. Resistance management required (UG)
				x	x					DIFENOCONAZOLE	Synthetic fungicide	DMI-fungicides(DeMethylationinhibitors)(SBI: Class I)	when first symptoms occur. Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest	2 (Among all SBIs)	(DISCO) Broad spectrum systemic fungicide that acts by contact, with preventive control of the activity. Dosage: 0.3-0.5 L/ha	Medium risk (3)
				x	x	x				FLUXAPYROXAD	Synthetic fungicide	Succinate dehydrogenase SDHI inhibitors	when first symptoms occur. Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest	3 (Among Boscalid, Fluopyram, Pentoxiprad, Fluxapyroxad, Isopyrazam)	(ALLSTAR) Dosage 0,15 L/ha. Fluxapyroxad shows a marked preventive activity, combined with a prolonged persistence over time	Medium to high risk (7)
		x		x					PENCONAZOLE	Synthetic fungicide	DMI-fungicides (DeMethylation inhibitors) (SBI: Class I)	from BBCH 14. Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest	2 (Among all SBIs)	(Topas® 10 EC) Dosage: 0,5L/ha. Broad spectrum systemic fungicide with preventive, curative and blocking activity	Medium risk (3)	
		x		x					PYRACLOSTROBIN	Synthetic fungicide	Qoi-fungicides(Quinone outsideinhibitors)	when first symptoms occur. Suspend treatments 7 days before harvest	3 (Between Pyraclostrobin, Tyfloxistrobin and Azoxystrobin)	(CABRIO TOP) Cover fungicide with preventive activity. Dosage: 1,5-2 Kg/ha	High risk (11)	
		x							TEBUCONAZOLE	Synthetic fungicide	DMI-fungicides(DeMethylationinhibitors)(SBI: Class I)	when first symptoms occur. Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest	2 (Among all SBIs)	(ARES 430 SC) Fungicide in concentrated suspension formulation with preventive, curative and eradicating action. Dosage: 500 ml/ha	Medium risk (3)	
		x							TETRACONAZOLE	Synthetic fungicide	DMI-fungicides(DeMethylationinhibitors)(SBI: Class I)	when first symptoms occur. Suspend treatments 7 days before harvest	2 (Among all SBIs)	(CONCORDE 12S) Broad spectrum systemic fungicide. Dosage: 0,2-0,36 L/ha	Medium risk (3)	
		x							Fluopyram	Synthetic fungicide	SDHI (Succinate dehydrogenase inhibitors)					
		x		x					Trifloxystrobin	Synthetic fungicide	Qoi-fungicides (Quinone outside inhibitors)	From pre-bloom to pre-harvest. Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest	3 (Between Pyraclostrobin, Tyfloxistrobin and Azoxystrobin)	(FLINT MAX) Dosage: 300 g/ha	High risk (11)	
		ADOPT-IPM solutions	x	x					Bupirimate	Synthetic fungicide	hydroxy- (2-amino-) pyrimidines	from BBCH 10 to BBCH 89. Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest	2	(NIMROD 250 EW) Dosage: 0,3 L/ha	Medium risk (4)	
			x	x					Metsulfone	Synthetic fungicide	aryl-phenylketones	treatments 2 days before harvest	2	(VIVANDO) Dosage: 0.3 L/ha	Medium risk (50)	
			x						ANT_CL	Cultural		Harvest (BBCH 81-89)		minimum of 700 liters of water per hectare. Suggested		
			x						ANY_Y	Biocontrol agent		From Flowering (BBCH 51-59) to post-harvest		during flowering, starting from 2 weeks after		
			x		x				Natural based Pesticide (EO-based)	Biological fungicide	Natural compound				Currently applied in the form of liquid droplets for targeted applications, spray application is what will be ultimately aimed at.	

Late blight (*Phytophthora infestans*)

Crop	Insect pests and diseases	Management solutions	Country							Solution/Practice/Active ingredient	Product category	Chemical group	Production stage (if possible with reference to BBCH scale)	Max number of application per year	Application Details and Notes (commercial product example)	Resistance risk (FRAC Code)		
			IT	FR	ES	BE	NL	DK	UK								CN	
Tomato	Late blight (<i>Phytophthora infestans</i>)	Agronomic tools	x	x	x						Aerate the greenhouse			From Sowing/Planting to Harvest				
			x	x	x						Drip irrigation			From Sowing/Planting to Harvest				
			x	x	x						Avoid stagnant water			From Sowing/Planting to Harvest				
		Genetic Tools																
		Monitoring				x												
		Physical methods																
		Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)	x	x	x							Copper fungicides	Biological fungicide	Inorganic	Start treatments before the onset of the disease and repeat them as needed	28 kg/ha in 7 years. It is recommended not to exceed the average quantity of 4 kg/ha of copper per year on the crop	(IDROX 20) Dosage: 2,5-3 Kg/ha	Low risk (M01)
						x						<i>Bacillus amyloliquifaciens</i> - FZB24	Microbiological fungicide					
						x						sweet orange essential	Biological fungicide					
		Chemical tools*	x									Metalaxyl-M	Synthetic fungicide	PA – fungicides (PhenylAmides)	Start of treatments since there are favorable conditions for the development of infection. Suspend treatments 20 days before harvest	3	(Metalaxyl-M) Dosage: 400 g/ha.	High risk (4)
			x	x	x							Cymoxanil	Synthetic fungicide	Cyanoacetamide-oxime	Start of treatments since there are favorable conditions for the development of infection. Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest	3	(CURZATE*) Dosage: 840 g/ha.	Low to medium risk (27)
			x	x								Mandipropamid	Synthetic fungicide	CAA-fungicides (Carboxylic Acid Amides)	Start of treatments since there are favorable conditions for the development of infection. Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest	4 (For all CAAs)	(PERGADO SC*) Dosage: 0,6 L/ha.	Low to medium risk (40)
			x	x								Ametoctradin	Synthetic fungicide	QoSI fungicides (Quinone outside inhibitor, stigmatellin binding type)	Start of treatments since there are favorable conditions for the development of infection. Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest	3	(ENERVIN* DUO) Dosage: 0,8 L/ha.	Medium to high (45)
			x		x							Propamocarb	Synthetic fungicide	Carbamates	Start of treatments since there are favorable conditions for the development of infection. Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest	2	(PREVICUR* ENERGY) Nursery, soil and foliar treatments possible. Read label to know dosages	Low to medium risk. (28)
			x	x	x							Pyraclostrobin	Synthetic fungicide	QoI-fungicides (Quinone outside inhibitors)	Start of treatments since there are favorable conditions for the development of infection. Suspend treatments 7 days before harvest	3 (Between Fenamidone, Pyraclostrobin, Trifloxystrobin and Azoxystrobin)	(CABRIO* TOP) Dosage: 1,5-2 L/ha.	High risk (11)
			x	x								Zoxamide	Synthetic fungicide	Benzamides	Start of treatments since there are favorable conditions for the development of infection. Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest	4	(ZOXIUM*240 SC) Dosage: 0,625-0,75 mL/ha.	Low to medium risk (22)
			x	x	x							Fosetyl-Aluminium	Synthetic fungicide	Phosphonates	Start of treatments since there are favorable conditions for the development of infection. Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest	2	(PREVICUR* ENERGY) Nursery, soil and foliar treatments possible. Read label to know dosages	Low level (P07)
			x									Fluazinam	Synthetic fungicide	Uncoupler of oxidative phosphorylation	Start of treatments since there are favorable conditions for the development of infection. Suspend treatments 7 days before harvest	2	(ZIGNAL) Dosage: 400 mL/ha.	Low risk (29)
			x									Oxathiopropin	Synthetic fungicide	OSBPI oxysterol binding protein homologue inhibition	Start of treatments since there are favorable conditions for the development of infection. Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest	3	(ZORVEC* ENICADE*) Dosage: 0,3 L/ha.	Medium to high (49)
x										Amisulbrom	Synthetic fungicide	QI - fungicides (Quinone inside inhibitors)	Start of treatments since there are favorable conditions for the development of infection. Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest	3	(LEIMAY) Dosage: 0,6 L/ha.	Resistance risk unknown but assumed to be medium to high (21)		
x	x		x							Cyazoflamid	Synthetic fungicide	QI - fungicides (Quinone inside inhibitors)	Start of treatments since there are favorable conditions for the development of infection. Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest	3	(RANMAN TOP) Dosage: 0,5 L/ha.	Resistance risk unknown but assumed to be medium to high (21)		

ADOPT-IPM solutions	x									ANT_BIOCHAR	Cultural		From pre-sowing to planting (BBCH 14)		Mix in the substrate before transplanting. Field 1-20 ton/ha, nursery 5-10% mixed with growing substrate
	x									ANT_CL	Cultural		From Post-emerg. - nursery (BBCH 05-13) to Harvest (BBCH 81-89)		Apply with foliar treatments at a dose of 2-4 l/ha with a minimum of 700 liters of water per hectare. Suggested concentration is 0.5% into water every 7-14 days when first symptoms occur
	x									ANT_COMPOST	Cultural		From pre-sowing to Planting (BBCH 14)		Mix in the soil or substrate before transplanting. In field 1-2 kg/m ² according to fertilization plan mixing into the soil. In nursery 10-20% mixed with growing media. Avoid the use on acidophilic crops
	x									ANT_HN	Bio-stimulant		season (BBCH 21-40)		and for fertigation systems (5-7 l/ha)
	x									ANT_HP	Cultural		From sowing (BBCH 09-13) to fruit development (BBCH 61-69)		Mix in aqueous solution and use to irrigate the soil or spray onto the leaves. Apply as a 1% or lower aqueous solution with a recommended dose of 3 to 5 l/ha by fertigation or leaf spray
	x									ANT_KH	Bio-stimulant		From pre-sowing to post-planting (BBCH 15-20)		Applicable by fertigation (10-20 l/ha). Can be used in preplanting or during transplanting (root dip) and for cuttings with maximum dosage of 3%
	x									ANT_MIX	Cultural		From post-emerg. (BBCH 05-13) to fruit development (BBCH 61-69)		mix in aqueous solution and use to irrigate the soil or spray the leaves. Foliar Treatments: apply in a maximum solution of 1% for high volumes and no more than 3%
	x									ANT_NTb	Cultural		From Planting (BBCH 14) to fruit development (BBCH 61-69)		mix in aqueous solution and irrigate the soil or spray the leaves. FOLIAR APPLICATION: Applications 2 to 5 during the cycle. Recommended dose: 0.5-2 l/ha. FERTIGATION: 0.5-1 l/ha, monthly.
	x									ANT_PL	Cultural		From post-emerg. (BBCH 05-13) to fruit development (BBCH 61-69)		mix in aqueous solution and use to irrigate the soil or spray the leaves. Applicable by foliar treatments (3-4 l/ha) and by fertigation systems (5-10 l/ha).
	x									ANT_PTb	Cultural		From Planting (BBCH 14) to Harvest (BBCH 81-89)		mix in aqueous solution and spray the leaves. FOLIAR APPLICATION: 50-100 ml per 100 L of broth, 2-5 applications during the cycle
x									ANT_RICCO	Cultural		From pre-sowing to planting (BBCH 14)		Mix to the soil from pre-season to pre-sowing according to the fertilization plan. Mix in soil or substrate before transplanting. Application dosage 1-2 l/ha, according to the fertilization plan.	

Wilts (*Fusarium oxysporum* f.sp. *lycopersici*) (*Verticillium dahliae*) (*Verticillium albo-atrum*)

Crop	Insect pests and diseases	Management solutions	Country							Solution/Practice/Active ingredient	Product category	Production stage (if possible with reference to BBCH scale)	Max number of application per year	Application Details and Notes (commercial product example)	Resistance risk (FRAC Code)		
			IT	FR	ES	BE	NL	DK	UK							CN	
Tomato	Wilts (<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> f.sp. <i>lycopersici</i>) (<i>Verticillium dahliae</i>) (<i>Verticillium albo-atrum</i>)	Agronomic tools	x	x							Avoid water stagnation		From Sowing/Planting to Harvest				
			x	x							Collect and destroy infected plants.		From Sowing/Planting to Harvest				
			x	x							Wide crop rotations		Pre-season				
			x	x							Carry out soil disinfection (where it is possible).		Pre-season				
		Genetic Tools	x	x	x						Use resistant or tolerant varieties		Sowing/Planting				
			Monitoring			x						Observation: presence/absence					
		Physical methods		x	x							Solarize the ground with transparent PE film with a thickness of mm 0.035-0.050		Pre-season			
			Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)	x								Application of BCAs starting from nursery		From Pre-sowing/Pre-planting to Harvest			
		x									Application of suppressive compost in nursery or in		From Pre-sowing/Pre-planting to Harvest				
		x		x							<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> strain QST 713	Microbiological fungicide	from BBCH 13 to BBCH 89	6	(SERENADE® ASO) Dosage: 4-8 l/ha.	Resistance not known (BM02)	
		x		x							<i>Pseudomonas</i> sp. DSMZ strain	Microbiological fungicide	First application in pre/transplant, and thereafter, for a maximum of 3 applications/crop cycle, every 15-30 days	3 per crop cycle	(Proradix®) Dosage: 100-125 g/ha. The first application can be by root wetting, fertigation or sprinkler. Subsequent ones by fertigation or sprinkler		
		x		x							Streptomyces k61	Microbiological fungicide	Immediately after the transplantation. Repeat the treatment every 3 to 6 weeks		(LALSTOP K61 WP) To be applied to the growing medium by soil drenching or drip irrigation at the time of transplanting. Use 2-10 g/100 m2 or 5-20 g/1000 plants	Resistance not known (BM02)	
		x									<i>Trichoderma asperellum</i> & <i>Trichoderma gamsii</i>	Microbiological fungicide	Apply by wetting the substrate in pre-sowing or pre-transplanting and	2 per crop cycle	(REMEDIER) Dosage: 2,5 kg/ha	Resistance not known (BM02)	
					x						<i>Trichoderma asperellum</i> & <i>Trichoderma atroviride</i>	Microbiological fungicide	The first application, of 1kg/ha, will be made at the time of the transplant and the rest 0.5 kg/ha at	5 per crop cycle	(TUSAL) Dosage: 0,5 - 1 kg/ha		
		x									<i>Clonostachys rosea</i> strain	Microbiological fungicide					
		ADOPT-IPM solutions	ANT_BIOCHAR	x							ANT_BIOCHAR	Cultural		From pre-sowing to planting (BBCH 14)		Mix in the substrate before transplantig. Field 1-20 ton/ha, nursery 5-10% mixed with growing substrate	
				x							ANT_CL	Cultural		From Post-emerg. - nursery (BBCH 05-13) to Harvest (BBCH 81-89)		Apply with foliar treatments at a dose of 2-4 l/ha with a minimum of 700 liters of water per hectare. Suggested concentraion is 0.5% into water every 7-14 days when first symptoms occur	
				x							ANT_COMPOST	Cultural		From pre-sowing to Planting (BBCH 14)		Mix in the soil or substrate before transplanting. In field 1-2 kg/m2 according to fertilization plan mixing into the soil. In nursery 10-20% mixed with growing media. Avoid the use on acidophilic crops	
				x							ANT_HN	Bio-stimulant		From Post-emerg. - nursery (BBCH 05-13) to growing season (BBCH 21-40)		Apply with foliar treatments (2-4 l/ha diluted to at least 1:200) and for fertigation systems (5-7 l/ha)	
				x							ANT_HP	Cultural		From sowing (BBCH 09-13) to fruit development (BBCH 61-69)		Mix in aqueous solution and use to irrigate the soil or spray onto the leaves. Apply as a 1% or lower aqueous solution with a recommended dose of 3 to 5 l/ha by fertigation or leaf spray	
				x							ANT_KH	Bio-stimulant		From pre-sowing to post-planting (BBCH 15-20)		Applicable by fertigation (10-20 l/ha). Can be used in preplanting or during transplanting (root dip) and for cuttings with maximum dosage of 1%	
				x							ANT_MIX	Cultural		From post-emerg. (BBCH 05-13) to fruit development (BBCH 61-69)		mix in aqueous solution and use to irrigate the soil or spray the leaves. Foliar Treatments: apply in a maximum solution of 1% for high volumes and no more than 3%	
				x								Cultural		From Planting (BBCH 14) to fruit development (BBCH 61-69)		mix in aqueous solution and irrigate the soil or spray the leaves. FOLIAR APPLICATION: Applications 2 to 5 during the cycle. Recommended dose: 0.5-2l/ha.	
											ANT_NTb					8	FERTIGATION: 0.5-1 l/ha, monthly.
									ANT_PL	Cultural		From post-emerg. (BBCH 05-13) to fruit development (BBCH 61-69)		mix in aqueous solution and use to irrigate the soil or spray the leaves. Applicable by foliar treatments (3-4 l/ha) and by fertigation systems (5-10 l/ha).			
							ANT_PTb	Cultural					mix in aqueous solution and spray the leaves. FOLIAR APPLICATION: 50-100 ml				

Grey mould (*Botrytis cinerea*)

Crop	Insect pests and diseases	Management solutions	Country					Solution/Practice/Active ingredient	Product category	Chemical group	Production stage (if possible with reference to BBCH scale)	Max number of application per year	Application Details and Notes (commercial product example)	Resistance risk (FRAC Code)	
			IT	FR	ES	BE	NL								DK
Tomato	Grey mould (<i>Botrytis cinerea</i>)	Agronomic tools	x	x	x			Aerate the greenhouse			From Sowing/Planting to Harvest				
			x	x	x			Use drip irrigation			From Sowing/Planting to Harvest				
			x	x				Avoid high crop density			Sowing/Planting				
								Clean the fields and reduce the number of bacteria sources							
								Using Bumblebee Pollination Instead of Dipping Flowers in Hormones							
				Genetic Tools											
				Monitoring	x	x			Observation: presence/absence						
									Check the flowers, fruits, and leaves every day from the early stage of fruit setting						
				Physical methods					Once you find gray mold on the surface of flowers and fruits or "U"-shaped spots on the leaf edges, start direct prevention and treatment						
									Manually remove diseased leaves and fruits and bury them deep						
				Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)	x	x			<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> strain CST 713	Microbiological fungicide		from BBCH 13 to BBCH 89	6	(SERENADE® ASO) Dosage: 4-8 L/ha.	Resistance not known (BW02)
					x				<i>Pythium oligactum</i> STRAIN M1	Microbiological fungicide		from BBCH 10 to BBCH 89	4	(POLYVERSUM®) Dosage: 200-300 g/ha	
					x	x			14940 and 14941	Microbiological fungicide		from BBCH 68 to BBCH 89	4	(BOTECTOR® New)	
					x	x			<i>Trichoderma atroviride</i> SC1	Microbiological fungicide		from BBCH 51 to BBCH 89	8	(VINTEC) Dosage: 50-100g/ha	
					x	x			<i>Bacillus amyloquelicifaciens</i> strain D747	Microbiological fungicide		from BBCH 70 to BBCH 89	6	(AMYLO-X) Dosage: 1.5-2.5 kg/ha	
					x	x			<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> LAS02	Microbiological fungicide		Apply preventively before a risk of infestation occurs	8	(SWOOSH®) Dosage: 2.5 kg/ha	
					x	x			Cerevisane	Biological fungicide		Apply preventively before a risk of infestation occurs	10	(ROME0) Dosage: 500g/ha	
								600	Microbiological fungicide						
				Chemical tools*	x	x			Fenpyrazamine	Synthetic fungicide	KRI fungicides (Ketoreductase Inhibitors) (SBI Class III)	Start of treatments since there are favorable conditions for the development of infection. Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest	2 (Same mechanism of action, limit the number of interventions between the two products to 2)	(PROLECTUS™ 50 WG) Dosage: 0,8-1,2 L/ha.	Low to medium risk. (17)
					x	x	x		Fenhexamid	Synthetic fungicide	KRI fungicides (Ketoreductase Inhibitors) (SBI Class III)	Start of treatments since there are favorable conditions for the development of infection. Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest	2 (Same mechanism of action, limit the number of interventions between the two products to 2)	(TELDOR PLUS) Dosage: 1-1,5 L/ha.	Low to medium risk. (17)
					x	x		x	Pyrimethanil	Synthetic fungicide	AP - fungicides (AnilinoPyrimidines)	Start of treatments since there are favorable conditions for the development of infection. Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest	2	(SCALA®) Dosage: 2 L/ha.	Medium risk. (9)
					x	x			Fludioxonil	Synthetic fungicide	PP-fungicides (PhenylPyrrroles)	Start of treatments since there are favorable conditions for the development of infection. Suspend treatments 7 days before harvest	2	(S W I T C H®) Dosage: 0,8 Kg/ha.	Low to medium risk. (12)
					x	x	x		Cyprodinil	Synthetic fungicide	PP-fungicides (PhenylPyrrroles)	Start of treatments since there are favorable conditions for the development of infection. Suspend treatments 7 days before harvest	2	(S W I T C H®) Dosage: 0,8 Kg/ha.	Medium risk. (9)
					x	x			Pyraclostrobin	Synthetic fungicide	QoI-fungicides (Quinone outside Inhibitors)	Start of treatments since there are favorable conditions for the development of infection. Suspend treatments 7 days before harvest	3 (Between Fenamidone, Pyradostrobin, Tryfloxistrobin and Azoxystrobin)	(CABRIO® TOP) Dosage: 1,5-2 L/ha.	High risk (11)
					x	x		x	Boscalid	Synthetic fungicide	SDH (Succinate dehydrogenase inhibitors)	when first symptoms occur	3 (Among Boscalid, Fluopyram, Penthiopyrad, Fluxapyroxad, Isopyrazam)	(BAS 51001 F) Contact fungicide with translaminar properties. Dosage 0,2 Kg/ha	Medium to high risk. (7)
		x	x				Penthiopyrad	Synthetic fungicide	SDH (Succinate dehydrogenase inhibitors)	Start of treatments since there are favorable conditions for the development of infection. Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest	3 (Among Boscalid, Fluopyram, Penthiopyrad, Fluxapyroxad, Isopyrazam)	(FONTEUS) Dosage: 2,4 L/ha.	Medium to high risk. (7)		
							Iprodione	Synthetic fungicide							
							Polymyacin	Synthetic fungicide							
						Procyimidone	Synthetic fungicide								

Crop	Insect pests and diseases	Management solutions	Country							Solution/Practice/Active Ingredient	Product category	Chemical group	Production stage (if possible with reference to BBCH scale)	Max number of application per year	Application Details and Notes (commercial product example)	IRAC code
			IT	FR	BE	NL	DK	CN								
Tomato	Whiteflies (<i>Trialeurodes vaporariorum</i>) (<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>)	Agronomic tools	x	x					Use suitable nets to screen all the openings of the greenhouses in order to prevent the entry of adult whiteflies.			From Sowing/Planting to Harvest				
					x				Avoid overlap with tomato plant cultivation	Routine agronomic practice		Treat throughout the growing season	3	Observation: presence/absence		
								x	Use proper supply of N fertilization							
								x	Rotate crops with vegetables such as celery, spinach, rapeseed, and garlic sprouts to reduce the source of overwintering insects.							
								x	In greenhouse seedling cultivation, weeds and remaining stumps and dead leaves should be thoroughly removed, insect-proof nets should be added to the ventilation holes to control foreign insect sources and cultivate insect-free seedlings.							
							x	Avoid planting with cucumbers and beans.								
							x	Increase ventilation and control humidity.								
							x	Use resistant varieties (such as Tigriss, Wanfeng 2)								
							x	Expose glass-paneled yellow panels for monitoring whitefly adults.								
							x	Threshold: 10 juvenile stage alive/leaf. Release 4-6 times about 4-6 puparium/m ² every 15 days during spring and every week during summer. A parasitization rate of 60-70% is enough for a good control.								
							x	Threshold: When the average of 1 adult whitefly per plant is reached in 30 plants in the lateral area, it will be necessary start <i>Macrolophus pygmaeus</i> introductions								
							x	Chemical treatments: in areas with a high risk of virosis, treat the beginning of the infestations.								
							x	Yellow board monitoring: After the tomatoes are planted, yellow boards are used to monitor the dynamics. The yellow boards are set between the rows at the same height as the plants. 10 yellow boards are set per mu and replaced every 45 days.								
							x	Florida conducted a fixed-point survey to detect whitefly adults on the young leaves that unfolded at the top of the plant. The survey was conducted every 3-5 days, with 10 leaves surveyed at each point.								
							x	When there are 5-10 adult insects on each leaf of the upper leaves of tomatoes, pesticides should be used for prevention and control in time.								
							x	Control threshold is 10-20 plants showing symptoms per acre and/or at least 20 whiteflies on at least 30 plants per acre (<i>Bemisia tabaci</i>)								
							x	Chemical treatments: in areas with a high risk of virosis, treat the beginning of the infestations; in the other areas, treat in the presence of 10 nymphs per leaf.								
							x	Use photoselective plastics with an insect repellent effect.								
							x	Savaguard natural populations of <i>Dicyphus dimidiatus</i>								
							x	Spray fermented chili + garlic liquid	Biological insecticide						Spray fermented chili + garlic liquid and leave in the sun for a week, using a concentration of 0.5-1 liter per 20 liters of	
							x	<i>Beauveria bassiana</i>	Microbiological insecticide							
							x	<i>Amblyseius swirski</i>	Predator							
							x	Several species of macro-org	Predators							
							x	Potassium salts of fatty acids	Biological insecticide							
							x	<i>Isaria fumosorosea</i> strain Apopka 97	Microbiological insecticide							
							x	<i>Paeicomyces fumosoroseus</i> strain FE 9901	Microbiological insecticide							
							x	Sweet orange essential oil	Biological insecticide	Natural compound		Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest	6	(PREV-AM® PLUS) Dosage: 4l/ha		
							x	Azadirachtin	Biological insecticide	Azadirachtin		Treat preventively or at the first appearance of parasites	5	(OIKOS®) Dosage: 1-1.5 L/ha	UN	
							x	Maltodextrins	Biological insecticide	Natural compound						
							x	Vegetal oil	Biological insecticide	Oil-seed rape						
							x	<i>Encarsia formosa</i>	Parasitoid (Macro-BCA)			Treat at the first appearance of pests	2 or 3			
							x	<i>Chrysoperla carnea</i>	Predator (Macro-BCA)			Treat at the first appearance of pests	2 or 3			
							x	Pure pyrethrins	Biological insecticide	Pyrethrins and pyrethrins		Treat preventively or at the first appearance of parasites	2	(Pyganic® 1.4) Dosage: max 2,5 L/ha	3A	
							x	Sulfoxalor	Synthetic insecticide	Sulfoximines		Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 1 day before harvest	1	(CLOSER™) Dosage: 200 ml/ha	4C	
							x	Acetamiprid	Synthetic insecticide	Neonicotinoids		Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 7 days before harvest	1 (For all neonicotinoids)	(EPIK® SL) Dosage: 2 l/ha	4A	
							x	Flupyradifurone	Synthetic insecticide	Butenolides		Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest	2	(SIVANTO® PRIME) Dosage: 0,56-1,125 L/ha	4D	
							x	Cytraniliprole	Synthetic insecticide	Diamides		Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 14 days before harvest	2 (Between Cytraniliprole and Cytraniliprole)	(MINECTO ALPHA TM) Dosage: 3l/ha	28	
							x	Pyriproxyfen	Synthetic insecticide	Oxylylidines		Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest	1	(ENIFUL) Dosage: 0,5-1,125 L/ha	7C	
							x	Bonicamid	Synthetic insecticide	Bonicamid		Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest	2	(TEPPEK®) Dosage: 0,10-0,12 Kg/ha. Only for hose or drip irrigation	29	
							x	deltamethrin	Synthetic insecticide	Pyrethroids						
							x	Pyrimidobenz and Thiamethoxam	Synthetic insecticide							
							x	Pyrethroid and Dinotefuran	Synthetic insecticide							
							x	Avemectin	Synthetic insecticide	Avemectin						
							x	Buprofezin	Synthetic insecticide						The usual concentration is 0,113-0,172 kg (active ingredient) per acre. Please use it after carefully reading the product label instructions. Buprofezin is an insecticide chitin synthesis inhibitor and can only control young whiteflies	
							x	Fluorourazole	Synthetic insecticide						to 378 liters of water. Please read the Mix: releasing with <i>Chrysoperla carnea</i> . According to commercial instructions	
					x	<i>Encarsia formosa</i>	Biocontrol agent			From Growing season (BBCH 23-40) to Fruit development (BBCH 61-69)			release of <i>Encarsia</i> wasps 500 wasps/667m ² , 10 days later, release of 500			
					x	<i>Encarsia formosa</i> reared with Yacon (<i>Smallanthus sonchifolius</i>) as host plant	Biocontrol agent			From Growing season (BBCH 23-40) to Fruit development (BBCH 61-69)			drip fertigation			
					x	Manipulation of nitrogen fertilization inputs	Plant resistance enhancement									
					x	Essential oil (Rosemary - <i>Salvia rosmarinus</i>)	Biological insecticide	Essential oil (Rosemary - <i>Salvia rosmarinus</i>)		From Planting (BBCH 14) to Pre-flowering (BBCH 41-50)			Fumigation (volatilised compound) with no direct contact with pest and the crop. Barrier and/or repulsive/push effect. Could be used as multi-pest target (for instance, pre-sowing use target soil parasitic nematodes) Disservice: Might attract <i>Tetranychus</i> (could be used as trap plant) Could be combined with Natural enemies,			

Aphids (*Myzus persicae*) (*Macrosiphum euphorbiae*) (*Aphis gossypii*)

Crop	Insect pests and diseases	Management solutions	Country							Solution/Practice/Active ingredient	Product category	Chemical group	Production stage (if possible with reference to BBCH scale)	Max number of application per year	Application Details and Notes (commercial product example)	IRAC code		
			IT	FR	ES	BE	NL	DK	UK								CN	
Tomato	Aphids (<i>Myzus persicae</i>) (<i>Macrosiphum euphorbiae</i>) (<i>Aphis gossypii</i>)	Agronomic tools																
		Genetic Tools																
		Monitoring	x x								Threshold: severe infestations							
			x x x								In areas at high risk of viruses: treat at the appearance of the first colonies							
			x x								In areas with low risk of viruses wait for at least 10% of the plants to be infested with colonies in growth before treat							
		Physical methods																
		Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)					x				Savaguard natural populations of natural predators (Aphidoletes aphidimyza, ladybugs, myriids) and parasitoids (Aphidius sp., Aphelinus sp., etc.) or introduce them.							
			x								Mineral oil	Biological insecticide	Organic compound	Treat preventively or at the first appearance				UNM
			x								Vegetal oil	Biological insecticide	Oil-seed rape					
			x x								Pure pyrethrins	Biological insecticide	Pyrethroids and pyrethrins	Treat preventively or at the first appearance of parasites	2	(Pyganic® 1.4) Dosage: max 2,5 L/ha	3A	
			x								Several species of macro-org predators & parasitoids							
			x x								Azadirachtin	Biological insecticide	Azadirachtin	Treat preventively or at the first appearance of parasites	5	(OIKOS®) Dosage: 1-1,5 L/ha	UN	
			x x								Potassium salts of fatty acids	Biological insecticide	Organic compound					
		Chemical tools*	x								Maltoedextrin	Biological insecticide	Natural compound					
			x								lambda-cyhalothrine	Synthetic insecticide	Pyrethroids					
			x								Sulfoxalor	Synthetic insecticide	Sulfoximines	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 1 day before harvest	1	(CLOSER™) Dosage: 200 ml/ha	4C	
			x								Acetamiprid	Synthetic insecticide	Neonicotinoids	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 7 days before harvest	1 (For all neonicotinoids)	(EPIK® SL) Dosage: 2 l/ha	4A	
			x								Flupyradifurone	Synthetic insecticide	Butenolides	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest		(SIVANTO® PRIME) Dosage: 0,56-1,125 L/ha	4D	
			x x x								flonicamid	Synthetic insecticide	flonicamid	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest		pericidae and Aphis gossypii) (TEPPEKI®) Dosage: 0,10-0,12 Kg/ha	29	
								x			Natural based Pesticide (EO-based)	Biological insecticide	Natural compound	Currently applied in the form of liquid droplets for targeted applications, spray application is what will be ultimately aimed at.				
ADOPT-IPM solutions	x								Fennel & green anise essential oils as aphicides	Biological insecticide	Natural compound	From Growing season (BBCH 21-40) to Harvest (BBCH 81-89)		Fumigation during 24h at the beginning of the pest infestation				
									Combination of aphid-based banker plant systems: (i) Faba bean with Aphis pisum targeting Aphis ervi, (ii) wheat with Rhopalosiphum padi targeting Adalia bipunctata	Biocontrol agent				number of BCA individuals released per plant and depending on infestation level to be defined, ratio of banker plants to crop plants to be defined				
									50% reduction of global fertilisation to reduce pest build-up	Cultural		From Post-planting (BBCH 15-20) to Harvest (BBCH 81-89)		Apply 50% less fertilisation by dividing concentration by 2 (dilute in water). Compatible with macroBCAs - both parasitoids and predators, as reducing fertilisation has no effect on them and even can have positive effects (particularly for the 2nd generation). The intermediate level of fertilisation needs to be chosen so as to maintain crop growth and optimal yield production.				

Tuta absoluta

Crop	Insect pests and diseases	Management solutions	Country						Solution/Practice/Active Ingredient	Product category	Chemical group	Production stage (if possible with reference to BBCH scale)	Max number of application per year	Application Details and Notes (commercial product example)	IRAC code	
			IT	FR	ES	BE	NL	DK								CN
		Agronomic tools	x	x					Use suitable nets to screen all the openings of the greenhouses in order to prevent the entry of adults.							
			x	x					Expose traps triggered with sex pheromone to monitor the flight of males and place electrofluorescent traps for mass trapping of adults.							
					x				Expose traps with sex pheromone to monitor the flight of males and traps for mass trapping of							
								x	Use proper supply of N fertilization	chemicals		Treat throughout the growing season	3			
								x	Intercropping with functional plant (as "pull" force)	Plant (under sorghum)		Grow the "pull" plants along the cash crop season	1			
		Genetic Tools														
		Monitoring	x						Threshold: presence of the pest.							
								x	Automated remote monitoring system & Appratus	Appratus		Established in the field margin		Permanent establishment		
				x					Threshold: low, medium, high or very high level							
			x						It is advisable to do chemical treatments when the first galleries appear on the leaves every as must be repeated twice at an interval of 7-10 days.							
		Physical methods														
		Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)			x				Secure the action of natural predators, like Macrolophus pygmaeus and Nesidiocoris tenuis (or introduce them), and other native parasitoids							
				x	x				Secure the action of natural predators, like Macrolophus caliginosus and Nesidiocoris tenuis and some Hymenoptera predators of eggs (Tricogramma spp.)							
				x	x				Use pheromone traps for monitoring the presence of the insect							
				x	x				Mating disruption							
				x	x	x			Bacillus thuringiensis kurstaki strain SA-11	Biological insecticide						
				x					Azadirachtin	Biological insecticide	Azadirachtin	Treat preventively or at the first appearance of parasites	5	(OIKOS®) Dosage: 1-1,5 L/ha	UN	
					x				Several species of macro-org	predators & parasitoids						
				x	x				Emamectin benzoate	Biological insecticide	Auematicins	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 3	3	(AFFIRM®) Dosage: 1.5 kg/ha	6	
								x	Chrysoperla carnea	Predator (Macro-BCA)		Treat at the first appearance of pests	2 or 3			
								x	Me-Jaemonic acid as "inducer"	Biological	phytohormone	Treat preventatively (during seeds)	1 or 2			
			x	x				Spinosad	Biological insecticide	Spinosine	Treat preventively or at the first appearance of parasites	3	(LASER) Dosage: 160-300 ml/ha	5		
		Chemical tools*	x					Etofenprox	Synthetic insecticide	Pyrethroids and pyrethrins	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 7	1 (Among all pyrethroids)	(TREBON® UP) Dosage: 0,5 L/ha	3A		
				x				Tebuhenzozide	Synthetic insecticide	Diacylhydrazines	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 3	2 (Between Tebuzenozide and	(MIMIC®) Dosage: 750 ml/ha	1B		
				x	x	x		Cyrantraniliprole	Synthetic insecticide	Diamides	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 14	2 (Between Cloranttraniliprole	(MINECTO ALPHA TM) Dosage: 1l/ha	2B		
					x			Cypermethrin	Synthetic insecticide	Pyrethroids						
				x	x			Abamectin	Synthetic insecticide	Auematicins	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 7	3	(VERTIMEC® EC) Dosage: 0,5-1,2 L/ha	6		

Thrips (*Frankliniella occidentalis*, *Thrips tabaci*)

Crop	Insect pests and diseases	Management solutions	Country						Solution/Practice/Active ingredient	Product category	Chemical group	Production stage (if possible with reference to BBCH scale)	Max number of application per year	Application Details and Notes (commercial product example)	IRAC code		
			IT	FR	ES	BE	NL	DK								CN	
Tomato	Thrips (<i>Frankliniella occidentalis</i> , <i>Thrips tabaci</i>)	Agronomic tools		x					Use healthy plants			Planting					
		Genetic Tools															
		Monitoring	x	x						Threshold: presence of the pest.							
					x					Threshold: presence of the							
		Physical methods															
			x							Release 1-2 predators/m2							
		Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)	x	x						Use chromotrophic traps (blue) for monitoring (1 every							
				x						Azadirachtin	Biological insecticide	Azadirachtin					
				x						Spinosad	Biological insecticide	Spinosine					
				x	x					<i>Amblyseius swirskii</i>	Predatory mite						
				x						Several species of macro-org	predators & parasitoids						
						x				Savaguard natural populations of predatory myrids.							
				x	x					<i>Beauveria bassiana</i>	Microbiological insecticide						
				x	x					Sweet orange essential oil	Biological insecticide	Natural compound		Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest	6	(PREV-AM® PLUS) Dosage: 4 l/ha	
					x					<i>Metarhizium brunneum</i> strain Ma43	Microbiological insecticide						
					x					<i>Paecilomyces fumosoroseus</i> strain FE 9901	Microbiological insecticide						
					x					Potassium salts of fatty acids	Biological insecticide	Organic compound					
			Chemical tools		x						Terpenoid blend QRD 460	Biological insecticide	Organic compound				
				x						Formetanate	Synthetic insecticide	Carbamates	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 14 days before harvest	1	(DICARZOL® 10 SP) Dosage: 5,50 kg/ha	1A	
				x						Cyantranilprole	Synthetic insecticide	Diamides	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 14 days before harvest	1 (Among all neonicotinoids)	(MINECTO ALPHA TM) Dosage: 1l/ha	28	
					x					Deltamethrin	Synthetic insecticide	Pyrethroids					
				x	x					Abamectin	Synthetic insecticide	Avermectins	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 7 days before harvest	3 (Between Abamectin and Emamectin)	(VERTIMEC®EC) Dosage: 0,3-1,2 L/ha	6	
				x				Spinosad	Synthetic insecticide	Spinosine	Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest	3 (Time interval between	(SPINTOR 480 sc®) Dosage: 20-25 cc/hl	5			
ADOPT-IPM solutions				x				Bumblebee entomovectoring system			Flowering (BBCH 51-59)						

Leaf Miner flies (*Liriomyza* spp.)

Crop	Insect pests and diseases	Management solutions	Country							Solution/Practice/Active ingredient	Product category	Chemical group	Production stage (if possible with reference to BBCH scale)	Max number of application per year	Application Details and Notes (commercial product example)	IRAC code
			IT	FR	ES	BE	NL	DK	CN							
Tomato	Leaf Miner flies (<i>Liriomyza</i> spp.)	Agronomic tools			x					remove basal leaves with the presence of mines						
		Genetic Tools														
		Monitoring	x	x						Apply yellow chromotropic traps to monitor the adults: when early leaf mines occur, carry out 1-2 releases of 0.1-0.5 individuals/m ² of <i>Diglyphus isaea</i> .						
						x				Threshold: low, medium, high or very high level						
		Physical methods														
		Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)	x	x						Spinosad	Biological insecticide	Spinosyns	Treat preventively or at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest	3	(LASER) Dosage: 160-300 ml/ha	5
					x					Azadirachtin	Biological insecticide	Azadirachtin				
						x				Introduction of the parasitoid <i>Diglyphus isaea</i>						
		Chemical tools*	x	x	x					Abamectin	Synthetic insecticide	Avermectins	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 7 days before harvest	3 (Between Abamectin and Emamectin)	(VERTIMEC®EC) Dosage: 0,3-1,2 L/ha	6
						x				Cyantraniliprole + Acibenzolar-S-methyl	Synthetic insecticide	Diamides and Benzothiadiazoles	Greenhouse treatments from the 2nd true leaf of the main stem, unfolded to the full ripeness: the fruits have the typical color of ripeness (BBCH 12-89). 3-day safety period for foliar application and 14 days for drip irrigation	1	(MINECTO ALPHA TM) Dosage: 1l/ha	28
		ADOPT-IPM solutions							x	<i>Chrysoperla carnae</i>	Biocontrol agent		From Growing season (BBCH 21-40) to Fruit development (BBCH 61-69)		Mix-releasing with <i>Encarsia formosa</i> . According to commercial instructions	
									x	Manipulation of nitrogen fertilization inputs	Plant resistance enhancement		From Planting (BBCH 14) to Fruit development (BBCH 61-69)		Drip fertigation	

Tomato russet mite (*Aculops lycopersici*)

Crop	Insect pests and diseases	Management solutions	Country							Solution/Practice/Active ingredient	Product category	Chemical group	Production stage (if possible with reference to BBCH scale)	Max number of application per year	Application Details and Notes (commercial product example)	IRAC code	
			IT	FR	ES	BE	NL	DK	CN								
Tomato	Tomato russet mite (<i>Aculops lycopersici</i>)	Agronomic tools															
		Genetic Tools															
		Monitoring			x					Threshold: presence/absence							
		Physical methods															
		Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)	x	x						<i>Amblyseius andersoni</i>	Predator						
			x							Potassium salts of fatty acids	Biological insecticide	Organic compound					
		ADOPT-IPM solutions	x	x	x					Sulfur	Biological fungicide	Inorganic	from BBCH 10 to BBCH 89	6	(Tiovit Jet) Dosage 1,5-5 Kg/ha. Tiovit Jet is not compatible with alkaline insecticides and mineral oils.		
			x							Abamectin	Synthetic insecticide	Avermectins					
						x				Formulated on a sulfur basis	Mineral acaricide	Mineral compound	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Only outdoors				
							x			Fenpyroximate	Synthetic insecticide	METI acaricides and insecticides	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 7 days before harvest	1	(FLASH®) Dosage: 0,1 - 0,125 L/ha	10A	
							x			Spiromesifen	Synthetic insecticide	Derivatives of tetrone and tetramic acids	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest	4	(OBERON®) Dosage: 0,04 - 0,06 %	23	
						x				<i>Transeius mondorensis</i>	Biocontrol agent		Growing season (BBCH 21-40)		release in the crop together with food		
				x				<i>Amblyseius</i> sp.	Biocontrol agent		Growing season (BBCH 21-40)		predatory mite (macro biological control agent)				
								Improved (stick) sachet systems for predatory mites	Biocontrol agent		Growing season (BBCH 21-40)		hang them on the plants at a medium height, far from heating conduits and avoiding direct sunlight				

Nesidiocoris tenuis

Crop	Insect pests and diseases	Management solutions	IT	FR	ES	BE	NL	DK	CN	Solution/Practice/Active ingredient	Product category	Chemical group	Production stage (if possible with reference to BBCH scale)	Max number of application per year	Application Details and Notes (commercial product example)	IRAC code	
Tomato	<i>Nesidiocoris tenuis</i>	Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)			x					Synthetic insecticide & natural pyrethroids							
		ADOPT-IPM solutions			x					Insectary plants to lower damaging populations							
					x					Plant species to manage <i>Nesidiocoris tenuis</i> populations				From Pre-season to Harvest (BBCH 81-89)			
										Powerfood 3.0: In-crop feeding systems to boost the BCAs	Biocontrol agent					Food to boost the development of BCAs. The application every 3-4 weeks of the food in the middle leaves modify the distribution pattern of <i>Nesidiocoris tenuis</i> throughout the strata of the plants.	
						x				decrease the risk of	Cultural			Post-planting (BBCH 15-20)			
				x							Fruit development (BBCH 61-69)						

Examples of IPM Packages on tomato

Example n°1 - Italy

Pests (pathogen, insect, weed...)	Baseline (Farmer's strategy/control)	ADOPT-IPM strategy
Powdery mildews	Monitoring (observation: presence/absence) + chemical (bupirimate + pyraclostrobin)	Monitoring (observation: presence/absence) + ADOPT (ANT-CL)
Powdery mildews	Monitoring (observation: presence/absence) + chemical (bupirimate + pyraclostrobin)	Monitoring (observation: presence/absence) + ADOPT (ANT-PTb)
Wilts (<i>Fusarium</i>)	Soil disinfestation	ADOPT (ANT-Compost)
Wilts (<i>Fusarium</i>)	Soil disinfestation	ADOPT (ANT-Biochar)
Wilts (<i>Fusarium</i>)	Soil disinfestation	ADOPT (ANT-NT+ANT-VA)
Root rots (<i>Pythium</i> , <i>Phytophthora</i>)	Chemical (metalaxyl-M)	ADOPT (ANT-Compost)
Root rots (<i>Pythium</i> , <i>Phytophthora</i>)	Chemical (metalaxyl-M)	ADOPT (ANT-Biochar)
Root rots (<i>Pythium</i> , <i>Phytophthora</i>)	Chemical (metalaxyl-M)	ADOPT (ANT-NT+ANT-VA)

Example n°2 - France

Pests (pathogen, insect, weed...)	Baseline (Farmer's strategy/control)	ADOPT-IPM strategy
Tomato russet mite (<i>Aculops lycopersici</i>)	Monitoring (observation: presence/absence) + biological control (<i>Amblyseius swirskii</i>)	Monitoring (observation: presence/absence) + ADOPT (release of biological control agent <i>Transeius mondorensis</i> + feeding)

Example n°3 - Spain

Pests (pathogen, insect, weed...)	Baseline (Farmer's strategy/control)	ADOPT-IPM strategy
Powdery mildews	Monitoring (observation: presence/absence) + chemical (azoxystrobin and Cyprodinil + Fludioxonil)	Monitoring (observation: presence/absence) + chemical (azoxystrobin)
<i>Aculops lycopersici</i>	Monitoring (mites counted on leaves) + Chemical treatments (wetable sulphur)	Monitoring (mites counted on leaves) + Wetable sulphur (preventive) + releases of the predatory mite <i>Transeius montdoriensis</i> (from AGROBIO) + food to enhance mite establishment
<i>Tuta absoluta</i>	Monitoring (galleries counts) + <i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i> treatments + Conservation biological control based on predatory mirids	Monitoring (galleries counts) + Releases of the parasitic wasp <i>Dolichogenidea gelechiidivoris</i> (own production)
<i>Helicoverpa armigera</i>	Monitoring (larvae and eggs counts) + <i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i> treatments + Conservation biological control based on predatory mirids	Monitoring (larvae and eggs counts) + Conservation biological control based in predatory mirids

Example n°4 - Italy

Pests (pathogen, insect, weed...)	Baseline (Farmer's strategy/control)	ADOPT-IPM strategy
<i>Tuta absoluta</i> / <i>Nesidiocoris tenuis</i>	Traps for monitoring (observation: presence/absence) + biocontrol agents (i.e., <i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>) + bioinsecticides (e.g., azadirachtin, etc.)	Traps for monitoring (observation: presence/absence) + biocontrol agents (i.e., <i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>) + Alternative plants (<i>Sesamum indicum</i> and <i>Verbena x hybrida</i>)

Example n°5 - China

Pests (pathogen, insect, weed...)	Baseline (Farmer's strategy/control)	ADOPT-IPM strategy
Tomato pinworm (<i>Tuta absoluta</i>)	Monitoring (observation: presence) + chemical (12% Chlorfenapyr · Lufenuron SC + Chlorantraniliprole SC)	Sex pheromone traps developed by BAAFS + Sticky paper, <i>Trichogramma ostrinae</i> produced by GZU ; Bt (G033A) developed by CAAS
Greenhouse whitefly (<i>Trialeurodes vaporariorum</i>)	Monitoring (observation: presence) + chemical (10% Cyantraniliprole OD + 20% Pyriproxyfen · Spirotetramat OD)	<i>Encarsia formosa</i> produced by GZU
Tomato gray mold and powdery mildew	chemical (40% Pyrimethanil WP + 11% Cyflufenamid · Tebuconazole SC)	Compound antimicrobial agent of <i>Bacillus</i> produced by CAU

Fusarium wilt (*Fusarium oxysporum* f. sp. *lactucae*)

Crop	Insect pests and diseases	Management solutions	Country					Solution/Practice/Active ingredient	Product category	Chemical group	Production stage (if possible with reference to BBCH scale)	Max number of application per year	Application Details and Notes (commercial product example)	Resistance risk (FRAC code)		
			FR	ES	BE	NL	DK								CN	
Lettuce	Fusarium wilt (<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i> f. sp. <i>lactucae</i>)	Agronomic tools	x	x					Wide crop rotations			Pre-season				
			x	x					Use healthy certified propagation materials			Sowing/Planting				
			x	x					Carry out soil disinfection (where it is possible)			Pre-season				
		Genetic Tools	x	x					Use resistant varieties			Sowing/Planting				
		Monitoring														
		Physical methods														
		Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)	x						<i>Trichoderma asperellum</i> & <i>Trichoderma gamsii</i>	Microbiological fungicide		Apply by wetting the substrate in pre-sowing or pre-transplanting and	3 per crop cycle	(REMEDIER) Dosage: 2.5 kg/ha	Resistance not known (BM02)	
			x	x					<i>Gliocladium catenulatum</i> strain J1446	Microbiological fungicide	<i>Clonostachys rosea</i>					
			x						<i>Bacillus subtilis</i> strain QST 713	Microbiological fungicide		from BBCH 13 to BBCH 89	4	(SERENADE® ASO) Dosage: 5 L/ha in open field	Not know (BM02)	
			x						<i>Trichoderma harzianum</i> rifaI	Microbiological fungicide				TRIANUM		
		Chemical tools (Start the treatments when first symptoms occur)	x						Fosetyl-AI	Synthetic fungicide	Phosphonates					
		ADOPT-IPM solutions	x						ANT_BIOCHAR	Cultural		14)		nursery 5-10% mixed with growing substrate		
			x						ANT_CL	Cultural		From Post-emerg. - nursery (BBCH 05-13) to Harvest (BBCH 49)		Apply with foliar treatments at a dose of 2-4 l/ha with a minimum of 700 liters of water per hectare. Suggested concentration is 0.5% into water every 7-14 days when first symptoms occur		
			x						ANT_COMPOST	Cultural		From pre-sowing to Planting (BBCH 14-16)		Mix in the soil or substrate before transplanting. In field 1-2 kg/m ² according to fertilization plan mixing into the soil. In nursery 10-20% mixed with growing media. Avoid the use on acidophilic crops		
			x						ANT_HN	Bio-stimulant		From sowing (BBCH 09-13) to late growing season (BBCH 46-48)		Apply with foliar treatments (2-4 l/ha diluted to at least 1:200) and for fertigation systems (5-7 l/ha)		
			x						ANT_HP	Cultural		From sowing (BBCH 09-13) to late growing season (BBCH 46-48)		Mix in aqueous solution and use to irrigate the soil or spray onto the leaves. Apply as a 1% or lower aqueous solution with a recommended dose of 3 to 5 l/ha by fertigation or leaf spray		
			x						ANT_KH	Bio-stimulant		From pre-sowing to planting (BBCH 14-16)		Applicable by fertigation (10-20 l/ha). Can be used in preplanting or during transplanting (root dip) and for cuttings with maximum dosage of 1%		
			x						ANT_MIX	Cultural		From sowing (BBCH 09-13) to late growing season (BBCH 46-48)		Mix in aqueous solution and use to irrigate the soil or spray the leaves. Foliar Treatments: apply in a maximum solution of 1% for high volumes and no more than 3%		
			x						ANT_NTb	Cultural		From Post-sowing (BBCH 09-13) to fruit development (BBCH 61-69)		Mix in aqueous solution and irrigate the soil or spray the leaves. FOLIAR APPLICATION: Applications 2 to 5 during the cycle. Recommended dose: 0.5-2l/ha. FERTIGATION: 0.5-1 L/ha, monthly.		
			x						ANT_PL	Cultural		From sowing (BBCH 09-13) to late growing season (BBCH 46-48)		Mix in aqueous solution and use to irrigate the soil or spray the leaves. Applicable by foliar treatments (3-4 l/ha) and by fertigation systems (5-10 l/ha).		
			x						ANT_PTb	Cultural		From sowing (BBCH 09-13) to Harvest (BBCH 48)		Mix in aqueous solution and spray the leaves. FOLIAR APPLICATION: 50-100 ml per 100 L of broth, 2-5 applications during the cycle		
			x						ANT_RICCO	Cultural		From pre-sowing to planting (BBCH 14)		Mix to the soil from pre-season to pre-sowing according to the fertilization plan. Mix in soil or substrate before transplanting. Application dosage 1-2 l/ha, according to the fertilization plan.		
									x	MBCAs (Bacillus sp. x Trichoderma sp. Formulations)	Microbiological fungicide		sowing -nursery			

Aphids (*Myzus persicae*) (*Uroleucon sonchi*) (*Nasonovia ribisnigri*) root Aphids (*Pemphigus bursarius*)

Crop	Insect pests and diseases	Management solutions	Country						Solution/Practice/Active ingredient	Product category	Chemical group	Production stage (if possible with reference to BBCH scale)	Max number of application per year	Application Details and Notes (commercial product example)	IRAC code
			IT	FR	ES	BE	NL	DK							
Lettuce	Aphids (<i>Myzus persicae</i>) (<i>Uroleucon sonchi</i>) (<i>Nasonovia ribisnigri</i>) root Aphids (<i>Pemphigus bursarius</i>)	Agronomic tools													
		Genetic Tools													
		Monitoring	x	x	x				Threshold: presence. Infestations are relevant in spring and autumn; in summer there is a natural decrease in populations						
		Physical methods	x	x	x				Soaking of seedlings before transplanting.			Pre-planting			
		Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)	x						Potassium salts of fatty acids	Biological insecticide	Organic compound				
			x	x	x				Pure pyrethrins	Biological insecticide	Pyrethroids and pyrethrins	Treat preventively or at the first appearance of parasites	3	(PIRETRO VERDE) Dosage: max 2,4 L/ha	3A
			x						<i>Beauveria bassiana</i> strain ATCC 74040	Biological insecticide	Microbiological insecticide				
			x	x					Maltodextrin	Biological insecticide	Organic compound				
			x						Conserve natural enemies (Syrphidae)	Biological control					
			x	x	x	x		x	<i>Chrysoperla lucasina</i>	Biocontrol agent	Treat at the first appearance of parasites.			10 or 20 eggs /m2	
		Chemical tools	x	x					Deltamethrin	Synthetic insecticide	Pyrethroids and pyrethrins	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 7 days before harvest	3 (For crop cycle with Pyrethroids and etofenprox)	(DECIS®EVO) Dosage: 0,3-0,5 l/ha	3A
			x	x	x				Lambda-cyhalothrin	Synthetic insecticide	Pyrethroids and pyrethrins	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 14 days before harvest	2	(KARATE ZEON®1.5) Dosage: 0,5 L/ha	3A
			x	x					Tau-Fluvalinate	Synthetic insecticide	Pyrethroids and pyrethrins	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 7 days before harvest	3 (For crop cycle with Pyrethroids and etofenprox)	(EVURE® PRO) Dosage 0,4 l/ha	3A
			x						Sulfoxaflor	Synthetic insecticide	Sulfoximines	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 7 days before harvest	1	CLOSER™	4C
			x						Acetamiprid	Synthetic insecticide	Neonicotinoids	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 10 days before harvest	1 (1 treatment per crop cycle, 2 per year)	(EPIK® SL) Dosage: 2L/ha	4A
			x	x					Pyrimicarb	Synthetic insecticide	Carbamate				
		ADOPT-IPM solutions				x			Predator combinations to control aphids	Biocontrol agent		From Planting (BBCH 14-16) to Harvest (BBCH 49)		Preventive biological control of pests. Before opening the bottle, set it horizontally and rotate to mix the content. Release the bugs in small boxes all over the crop, early in the morning or at sunset.	
						x			Field margins and islands of vegetation to support BCAs	Cultural		Pre-season		New selection of native subarbutive species and new design of funtional biodiversity strategies	
					x				Genetic manipulation of pest			From Early growing season (BBCH 13-30) to late growing season (BBCH 46-48)		Application instructions to be defined: several modes of application may be tested, including ingestion (spray) and injection (which is not commercially realistic). Knockdown of genes involved in feeding in pests, next generation unable of feeding and dies	
							x		RNAi targeting pest feeding			Post-sowing (BBCH 09-13) to Late growing season (BBCH 46-48)		crop diversification to reduce host plant finding of herbivores and enhancing natural enemies	
						x			Plant species to support predators for aphid control in lettuce	Cultural		From Pre-season to Harvest (BBCH 49)		Currently some farmers are using margins of <i>Lobularia maritima</i> . Addition of other plant species is under development	

Thrips (*Thrips tabaci*, *T. fuscipennis*) (*Frankliniella occidentalis*)

Crop	Insect pests and diseases	Management solutions	Country						Solution/Practice/Active ingredient	Product category	Chemical group	Production stage (if possible with reference to BBCH scale)	Max number of application per year	Application Details and Notes (commercial product example)	IRAC code	
			IT	FR	ES	BE	NL	DK								CN
Lettuce	<i>Thrips (Thrips tabaci, T. fuscipennis) (Frankliniella occidentalis)</i>	Agronomic tools														
		Genetic Tools														
		Monitoring														
		Physical methods														
		Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)	x	x						Potassium salts of fatty acids	Biological insecticide	Organic compound	Treat preventively or at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 3 days	3	(LASER) Dosage: 250 ml/ha	5
			x	x	x					Spinosad	Biological insecticide	Spinosine				
			x							<i>Beauveria bassiana</i> strain GHA	Biological insecticide	Microbiological insecticide				
		Chemical tools	x	x	x	x	x		x	<i>Chrysoperla lucasina</i>	Biocontrol agent		Treat at the first appearance of parasites.		10 or 20 eggs /m2	0
			x							Etofenprox	Synthetic insecticide	Pyrethroids and pyrethrins	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 7 days before harvest	3 (For crop cycle with Pyrethroids and etofenprox)	TREBON* UP	3A
			x							Abamectin	Synthetic insecticide	Avermectins	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 7 days before harvest		(SUPERBO 18 EC) 50-100 ml/hl	6
			x	x						Acetamiprid	Synthetic insecticide	Neonicotinoids	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 10 days before harvest	1 (1 intervention per crop cycle, 2 per year)	(EPIK* SL) Dosage: 2L/ha	4A
		ADOPT-IPM solutions				x				Predator combinations to control aphids and other pests on lettuce	Biocontrol agent		Early growing season (BBCH 13-30)		Preventive biological control of pests. Before opening the bottle, set it horizontally and rotate to mix the content. Release the bugs in small boxes all over the crop, early in the morning or at sunset.	
						x				Field margins and islands of vegetation to support BCAs	Cultural		Pre-season		New selection of native subarbutive species and new design of funtional biodiversity strategies	
						x				Powerfood 3.0; In-crop feeding systems to boost the BCAs	Biocontrol agent		Early growing season (BBCH 13-30)		Food to boost the development of BCAs	
						x				Bumblebee entomovectoring system	Biocontrol agent		Flowering (BBCH 51-59)			

Weeds

Crop	Management solutions	Production stage	Weeds	Country						Solution/Practice/Active ingredient	NOTE	Expiry of Approval		
				IT	FR	ES	BE	NL	DK				CN	
Lettuce	Agronomic tools									x	false seed bed			
	Physical methods													
	Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)													
	ADOPT-IPM solutions	From Post-emergence (BBCH 10-19) to Post-harvest	Ambrosia artemisiifolia								x	Large mass rearing system of <i>Ophraella communa</i>	Biocontrol agent. Predator of the weed <i>A. artemisiifolia</i>	
	Chemical tools	Pre-sowing or transplant	Gramineae and Dicotyledons	x	x							Glyphosate	Only preparation of sowing or transplanting beds.	15/12/2033
				x	x							Pelargonic acid		01/12/2026
		Pre-transplant; Pre-sowing; Post-transplant; Post-sowing	Gramineae and Dicotyledons	x	x							Propyzamide		30/06/2025
Pre-transplant		Gramineae and Dicotyledons	x	x							Pendimethalin		15/01/2027	
Post-emergency		Gramineae									x	fluazifop		31/05/2026
											x	propaquizafop		28/02/2027
			x	x							Cycloxydim		31/08/2026	

Examples of IPM Packages on lettuce

Example n°1 - Italy

Pests (pathogen, insect, weed...)	Baseline (Farmer's strategy/control)	ADOPT-IPM strategy
Root rots (<i>Pythium</i> , <i>Rhizoctonia</i> , <i>Sclerotinia minor</i>)	Chemical (Ciprodinil fludioxonil)	ADOPT (ANT-Compost)
Root rots (<i>Pythium</i> , <i>Rhizoctonia</i> , <i>Sclerotinia minor</i>)	Chemical (Ciprodinil fludioxonil)	ADOPT (ANT-Biochar)
Root rots (<i>Pythium</i> , <i>Rhizoctonia</i> , <i>Sclerotinia minor</i>)	Chemical (Ciprodinil fludioxonil)	ADOPT (ANT-NT+ANT-VA)
Wilts (<i>Fusarium</i>)	No fungicides were used	ADOPT (ANT-Compost)
Wilts (<i>Fusarium</i>)	No fungicides were used	ADOPT (ANT-Biochar)
Wilts (<i>Fusarium</i>)	No fungicides were used	ADOPT (ANT-NT+ANT-VA)

Example n°2 - France

lettuce aphids (<i>Macrosiphum euphorbiae</i>)	Monitoring (observation: presence/absence) + chemical (spirotetramate)	Monitoring (observation: presence/absence) + ADOPT (flower strip to increase the presence of natural enemies + release of <i>Chrysoperla lucasina</i> eggs with PULZOR backpack sprayer)
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Example n°3 - Spain

Pests (pathogen, insect, weed...)	Baseline (Farmer's strategy/control)	ADOPT-IPM strategy
currant-lettuce aphid (<i>Nasonovia ribisnigri</i>)	No insecticides or fungicides were used. Conservation biological control.	Monitoring + Releases of <i>Chrysoperla lucasina</i> eggs (from IfTech).

CABBAGE

The cabbage IPM package is shown on the following pages. Each sheet is related to a different pest (pathogen, insect, weed), with the corresponding management solutions.

Aphids (*Brevicoryne brassicae*; *Myzus persicae*) (*Agriotes* spp.)

Crop	Insect pests and diseases	Management solutions	Country							Solution/Practice/Active ingredient	Product category	Chemical group	Production stage (if possible with reference to BBCH scale)	Max number of application per year	Application Details and Notes (commercial product example)	IRAC code	
			IT	FR	ES	BE	NL	DK	CN								
Cabbage	Aphids (<i>Brevicoryne brassicae</i> ; <i>Myzus persicae</i>) (<i>Agriotes</i> spp.)	Agronomic tools	x							Destroy cabbage stems after harvesting in winter.			Harvest				
		Genetic Tools															
		Monitoring															
		Physical methods															
		Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)	x								Maltodextrin	Biological Insecticide					
			x								Azadirachtin	Biological Insecticide					UN
		Chemical tools	x	x							Deltamethrin	Chemical insecticide	Pyrethroids and pyrethrins	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 7 days before harvest	2 per cycle with pyrethroids; 4 for cycles over 70 days.	(DECIS®EVO) Dosage: 0,3-0,5 l/ha	3A
			x	x							Cypermethrin	Chemical insecticide	Pyrethroids and pyrethrins	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 14 days before harvest	3 per cycle with pyrethroids; 4 for cycles over 70 days.	CYPERKILL 50 EC (1 L/ha)	3A
			x	x	x						Lambda-cyhalothrin	Chemical insecticide	Pyrethroids and pyrethrins	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 14 days before harvest	3 per cycle with pyrethroids; 4 for cycles over 70 days.	(KARATE ZEON®1.5) Dosage: 0,5 L/ha	3A
			x								Tau-Fluvalinate	Chemical insecticide	Pyrethroids and pyrethrins	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 7 days before harvest	pyrethroids; 4 for cycles over 70 days.	(EVURE® PRO) Dosage 0,4 l/ha	3A
			x								Sulfoxalor	Chemical insecticide	Sulfoximines	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 7 days before harvest	1	CLOSER™	4C
			x	x							Acetamiprid	Chemical insecticide	Neonicotinoids	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 14 days before harvest	1 (1 intervention per crop cycle, 2 per year)	(EPIK® SL) Dosage: 1,6L/ha. Acetamiprid allowed only on Brussels sprouts	4A
		ADOPT-IPM solutions		x							Predator combinations to control aphids and other pests on lettuce	Biocontrol agent		Early growing season (BBCH 13-30)		Preventive biological control of pests	
					x						Field margins and islands of vegetation to support BCAs	Cultural		Pre-season		New selection of native subarabustive species and new design of functional biodiversity strategies	
				x							RNAi targeting pest feeding	Genetic manipulation of pest		From Early growing season (BBCH 13-30) to late growing season (BBCH 46-48)		Application instructions to be defined: several modes of application may be tested, including ingestion (spray) and injection (which is not commercially realistic). Knockdown of genes involved in feeding in pests, next generation unable of feeding and dies	
						x					Stripcropping	Cultural		season (BBCH 46-48)		plant finding of herbivores and	
							x				Utility plants	Cultural		season (BBCH 46-48)		plant finding of herbivores and attracting parasitoids via enhanced	
								x			Attractive cultivar for parasitoids	Cultural		Post-sowing (BBCH 09-13) to Late growing season (BBCH 46-48)		HIPV emission of herbivore attacked plants	

Phyllotreta sp.

Crop	Insect pests and diseases	Management solutions	Country							Solution/Practice/Active Ingredient	Product category	Chemical group	Production stage (if possible with reference to BBCH scale)	Max number of application per year	Application Details and Notes (commercial product example)	IRAC code	
			IT	FR	ES	BE	NL	DK	CN								
Cabbage	Phyllotreta sp.	Agronomic tools															
		Genetic Tools															
		Monitoring															
		Physical methods					x			Strip cropping							
		Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)						x									
		Chemical tools*	x	x							Deltamethrin	Synthetic insecticide	Pyrethroids and pyrethrins	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 7 days before harvest	2 per cycle with pyrethroids; 4 for cycles over 70 days.	(DECIS®EVO) Dosage: 0,3-0,5 l/ha	3A
			x								Etofenprox	Synthetic insecticide	Pyrethroids and pyrethrins	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 7 days before harvest	3 (For crop cycle with Pyrethroids and etofenprox)	TREBON® UP Dosage 0,5L/ha	3A
			x								Acetamiprid	Synthetic insecticide	Neonicotinoids	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 14 days before harvest	1 (1 intervention per crop cycle, 2 per year)	(EPIK® SL) Dosage: 1,6L/ha. Acetamiprid allowed only on Brussels sprouts	4A
		ADOPT-IPM solutions				x					stripcropping	cultural		growing season (BBCH 46-48)		host plant finding of	
						x					Utility plants	cultural		growing season (BBCH 46-48)		host plant finding of	

Pieris brassicae

Crop	Insect pests and diseases	Management solutions	Country					Solution/Practice/ Active ingredient	Product category	Chemical group	Expiry of Approval	Production stage (if possible with reference to BBCH scale)	Max number of application per year	Application Details and Notes (commercial product example)	IRAC code	
			IT	FR	ES	BE	NL									DK
Cabbage	Pieris brassicae	Agronomic tools														
		Genetic Tools														
		Monitoring														
		Physical methods														
		Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)	x	x					<i>Thuringiensis</i> Subsp. <i>Kurstaki</i>	Microbiological insecticide				3		
			x	x					Spinosad	Biological insecticide	Spinosine			Maximum 3 interventions between Spinosad and Spinetoram		
			x						Azadirachtin	Biological insecticide	Azadirachtin			3		
		Chemical tools	x						Etofenprox	Synthetic insecticide	Pyrethroids and pyrethrins	31/03/2027	Treat at the first appearance of parasites.	3 (For crop cycle with 3 per cycle with pyrethroids; 4 for cycles over 70 days.	TREBON® UP Dosage 0.5L/ha	3A
			x	x					Cypermethrin	Synthetic insecticide	Pyrethroids and pyrethrins	31/01/2029	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 14 days before harvest	2 per cycle with pyrethroids; 4 for cycles over 70 days.	CYPERKILL 50 EC (1 L/ha)	3A
			x	x					Deltamethrin	Synthetic insecticide	Pyrethroids and pyrethrins	15/08/2026	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 7 days before harvest	2 per cycle with pyrethroids; 4 for cycles over 70 days.	(DECIS®EVO) Dosage: 0.3-0.5 l/ha	3A
			x	x					Lambda-cyhalothrin	Synthetic insecticide	Pyrethroids and pyrethrins	31/08/2026	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 14 days before harvest	3 per cycle with pyrethroids; 4 for cycles over 70 days.	(KARATE ZEON®1.5) Dosage: 0.5 L/ha	3A
			x						Emanectin Benzoate	Synthetic insecticide	Avermectins	15/11/2026	Treat at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 3 days before harvest	2	AFFIRM® 1.5L/ha	6
		ADOPT-IPM solutions						x	stripcropping	cultural			Post-sowing (BBCH 09-13) to Late growing season (BBCH 46-48)		crop diversification to reduce host plant finding of herbivores and enhancing natural enemies	
								x	Utility plants	cultural			Post-sowing (BBCH 09-13) to Late growing season (BBCH 46-48)		crop diversification to reduce host plant finding of herbivores and enhancing natural enemies	
								x	Attractive cultivar for parasitoids	cultural			Post-sowing (BBCH 09-13) to Late growing season (BBCH 46-48)		attracting parasitoids via enhanced HIPV emission of herbivore attacked plants	

Weeds

Crop	Management solutions	Production stage	Weeds	Country							Solution/Practice/Active ingredient	NOTE			
				IT	FR	ES	BE	NL	DK	CN					
Cabbage	Agronomic tools														
	Physical methods														
	Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)														
	ADOPT-IPM solutions	From Post-emergence (BBCH)	Ambrosia artemisiifolia			x						Large mass rearing system of <i>Ophraella communa</i>	Biocontrol agent. Predator of the weed <i>A. artemisiifolia</i>		
	Chemical tools	Pre-sowing or transplant	Gramineae and Dicotyledons	x								Glyphosate	Company limit on the use of glyphosate on non-tree crops		
				x								Pelargonic acid			
		Pre-transplant	Gramineae and Dicotyledons	x				x				Napropamide	Allowed only on cabbage		
				x	x							Pendimethalin			
		Post-emergency and Post-transplant	Dicotyledons	Dicotyledons	x								Clopyralid		
					x								Pyridates		
					x									Propaquizafop	Cap only. Check the authorizations of the formulations used
					x									Quizalofop ethyl isomer D	
x													Quizalofop-p-ethyl		
x					x								Cycloxydim		
Dicotyledons and Gramineae	Dicotyledons and Gramineae	Dicotyledons and Gramineae	x				x				Metazachlor	No more than 1 kg/ha of active substance in a period of 3 years on the same plot. Check registration on C. of Brussels			

WHEAT

The wheat IPM package is shown on the following pages. Each sheet is related to a different pest (pathogen, insect, weed), with the corresponding management solutions.

Fusariosis of cereals (*Fusarium* spp.)

Crop	Insect pests and diseases	Management solutions	Country					Solution/Practice/Active ingredient	Product category	Chemical group	Production stage (if possible with reference to BBCH scale)	Max number of application per year	Application Details and Notes (commercial product example)	Resistance risk (FRAC code)		
			IT	FR	ES	BE	NL								DK	CN
Wheat	Fusariosis of cereals (<i>Fusarium</i> spp.)	Agronomic tools	x	x	x				wide crop rotations			Pre-season				
			x	x	x					bury previous crop			From Sowing/Planting to			
			x	x	x					avoid sprinkler irrigation			Pre-season			
									Cultivar mixture							
				Genetic Tools						selection of resistant plant material						
				Monitoring												
				Physical methods												
				Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)	x	x				<i>Pythium oligandrum</i> Strain M1	Biological fungicide		From BBCH 30 to BBCH 69	2	(POLYVERSUM®) Dosage: 100-300 g/ha	
					x	x				K bicarbonate	Biological fungicide	Inorganic	From BBCH 61 to BBCH 77	2	(MALLEN®) Dosage: 5 kg/ha	
										<i>Bacillus</i>	Biological fungicide	biological	BBCH 30-65			
									<i>Clonostachys rosea</i>	Biological fungicide	biological	BBCH 30-65				
				Chemical tools	x					Pyraclostrobin	Synthetic fungicide	QoI outer membrane quinone inhibitors	From BBCH 20 to BBCH 59	2	(COMET® 250 EC) Dosage: 0,7-1 L/ha	High risk (11)
					x					Tetraconazole	Synthetic fungicide	DMI - demethylation inhibitors - BEI Class I	From BBCH 40 to BBCH 59	2	(EMERALD 40 EW) Dosage: 3 L/ha	Medium risk (3)
					x	x	x			Prothioconazole	Synthetic fungicide	DMI - demethylation inhibitors - BEI Class I	From BBCH 39 to BBCH 59	2	(PROSARO®) Dosage: 1 L/ha	Medium risk (3)
					x	x				Difenoconazole	Synthetic fungicide	DMI - demethylation inhibitors - BEI Class I	From BBCH 39 to BBCH 59	2	(TIPTOR ULTRA) Dosage: 1 L/ha	Medium risk (3)
					x	x				Bromuconazole	Synthetic fungicide	DMI - demethylation inhibitors - BEI Class I	From BBCH 30 to BBCH 59	2	(NINEVI®) Dosage: 1 L/ha	Medium risk (3)
					x	x	x			Tebuconazole	Synthetic fungicide	DMI - demethylation inhibitors - BEI Class I	From BBCH 50 to BBCH 59	2	(FOLICUR® WG) Dosage: 1 kg/ha	Medium risk (3)
					x	x	x			Metconazole	Synthetic fungicide	DMI - demethylation inhibitors - BEI Class I	From BBCH 20 to BBCH 59	2	(APTREL®) Dosage: 1L/ha	Medium risk (3)
									Mefenfluanolone	Synthetic fungicide	DMI - demethylation inhibitors - BEI Class I	From BBCH 20 to BBCH 59				
									Cultivar mixture	Genetic (resistant varieties, etc.)			From Sowing to Harvest (BBCH 90-91)		The mixture should be composed of 3-4 cultivars with varying level of resistance.	
				ADOPT-IPM solutions						Holistic IPM approach in wheat-based cropping systems	A mix of cultural, genetic, and conservation biological control				The template is not fully adapted to describe the IPM solution, based on a large combination of options for landscape management (grass & flower strips, multispecific hedgerows to attract beneficial organisms) and cultural management (crop rotation, resistant cultivars, intercropping, sowing date, companion crops, moderate fertilisation, mechanical weeding), targeting all main weeds (blackgrass, ryegrass, Galium aparine, ...), diseases (septoria, rusts,...) and invertebrate pests (aphids, slugs) in wheat-based cropping systems	

Wheat Powdery mildew (*Blumeria graminis*)

Crop	Insect pests and diseases	Management solutions	Country				Solution/Practice/Active ingredient	Product category	Chemical group	Production stage (if possible with reference to BBCH scale)	Max number of application per year	Application Details and Notes (commercial product example)	Resistance risk (FRAC code)				
			IT	FR	ES	BE								NL	DK	CN	
Wheat	Wheat Powdery mildew (<i>Blumeria graminis</i>)	Agronomic tools	x					x	wide crop rotations			Pre-season					
			x						x	bury previous crop residues			Pre-season				
			x							avoid sprinkler irrigation			From Sowing to Harvest				
		Genetic Tools							x	In case of infection, clean up crop residue to prevent overwintering of mildew. In case no major pests or diseases, leave residues in the field to improve soils.							
									x	Plant non-dense, for example 225 plants/m ² because dense vegetation may be conducive for spread of disease							
		Monitoring							x	Use resistant varieties, such as Zhengmai 366, Zhournal 18, Zhengyuan 987, and others.							
									x	selection of resistant plant material							
			x	x						Tripping threshold: 10-12 pustules evenly distributed on the last 2 leaves.							
		Physical methods							x	Monitor from late February from wheat heading period until pustulation period.							
									x	Choose 10 random points in the field. At every point investigate 3 to 5 plants. Monitor once a week.							
		Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)							x	Consider action when early first white spots occur on 5-15% of all plants.							
									x	Remove the infected leaves or plants, if few.							
		Chemical tools							x	Sulfur	Inorganic fungicide	Inorganic sulfur	Start of treatments since there are favorable conditions for the	1	(Zolfo Flow MCT) Dosage: 5-7 kg/ha Sorya Bacillus subtilis (特嘉曼菌剂). Make sure to choose a		
									x	Bacillus subtilis	Microbiological fungicide						
										x	Pyraclostrobin	Synthetic fungicide	QoI outer membrane quinone inhibitors	From BBCH 20 to BBCH 69	2	COMET® 250 EC) Dosage: 0.7-1 L/ha	High risk (11)
										x	Bixafen	Synthetic fungicide	SDHI - Succinate Dehydrogenase Inhibitors	From BBCH 30 to BBCH 50	2	(ASCRA® XP90) Dosage: 1.2-1.5 L/ha	Medium to high risk (7)
										x	Fluxapyroxad	Synthetic fungicide	SDHI - Succinate Dehydrogenase Inhibitors	From BBCH 25 to BBCH 69	2	(PRIAXOR®) Dosage: 1-1.5 L/ha	Medium to high risk (7)
										x	Tebuconazole	Synthetic fungicide	DMI - demethylation inhibitors - BEI Class I	From BBCH 30 to BBCH 49	2	(FOLIICUR® WG) Dosage: 1 kg/ha	Medium risk (3)
										x	Metconazole	Synthetic fungicide	DMI - demethylation inhibitors - BEI Class I	From BBCH 20 to BBCH 69	2	(APPREL®) Dosage: 1 L/ha	Medium risk (3)
										x	Prothioconazole	Synthetic fungicide	DMI - demethylation inhibitors - BEI Class I	From BBCH 30 to BBCH 69	2	(PROSAROP®) Dosage: 1 L/ha	Medium risk (3)
										x	Bromuconazole	Synthetic fungicide	DMI - demethylation inhibitors - BEI Class I	From BBCH 30 to BBCH 69	2	(NINEVP®) Dosage: 1 L/ha	Medium risk (3)
										x	Tetraconazole	Synthetic fungicide	DMI - demethylation inhibitors - BEI Class I	From BBCH 40 to BBCH 69	1	(EMERALD 40 EW) Dosage: 3 L/ha	Medium risk (3)
										x	Trifloxystrobin	Synthetic fungicide	QoI outer membrane quinone inhibitors				
										x	Fenpropidin	Synthetic fungicide	Amines - IBE-Class II morpholines				
										x	Spiraxamine	Synthetic fungicide	Amines - IBE-Class II morpholines	From BBCH 20 to BBCH 69	1	(SOUGOR®) Dosage: 0.7-1 L/ha	risk (5)
										x	Cyflufenamid	Synthetic fungicide	FRAC 10S				
										x	Pyrisulfone	Synthetic fungicide	FRAC 50				
									x	Metasulfone	Synthetic fungicide	FRAC 50					
									x	Proquinazid	Synthetic fungicide	FRAC 13					
		ADOPT-IPM solutions							x	Triadimefon	Synthetic fungicide		Spray in the early stage of disease.		(for example 粉锈宁 15% triadimefon wettable powder). Systemic action. Usually applied at 8.75g-15g (35-60g miscible oil) /75-100L water		
							x	Holistic IPM approach in wheat-based cropping systems	A mix of cultural, genetic, and conservation biological control				The template is not fully adapted to describe the IPM solution, based on a large combination of options for landscape management (grass & flower strips, multispecific hedgerows to attract beneficial organisms) and cultural management (crop rotation, resistant cultivars, intercropping, sowing date, companion crops, moderate fertilisation, mechanical weeding), targeting all main weeds (blackgrass, ryegrass, Galium aparine, ...), diseases (septoria, rusts, ...) and invertebrate pests (aphids, slugs) in wheat-based cropping systems				
							x	Strip cropping (oats)	Cultural				crop diversification to reduce host plant finding of herbivores and enhancing natural enemies				

WHEAT FOLIAR SEPTORIOSIS COMPLEX (*Stagonospora* sp, *Septoria* sp.)

Crop	Insect pests and diseases	Management solutions	Country					Solution/Practice/Active ingredient	Product category	Chemical group	Production stage (if possible with reference to BBCH scale)	Max number of application per year	Application Details and Notes (commercial product example)	Resistance risk (FRAC code)			
			IT	FR	ES	BE	NL								DK	CN	
Wheat	WHEAT FOLIAR SEPTORIOSIS COMPLEX (<i>Stagonospora</i> sp, <i>Septoria</i> sp.)	Agronomic tools	x	x					wide crop rotations			Pre-season					
			x	x					bury previous crop			Pre-season					
			x	x					avoid sprinkler irrigation			From Sowing to Harvest					
		Genetic Tools															
		Monitoring															
		Physical methods															
		Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)	x							<i>Pythium oligandrum</i> Strain M1	Microbiological fungicide		From BBCH 30 to BBCH 69	2	(POLYVERSUM®) Dosage: 100-300 g/ha		
			x							Sulfur	Inorganic fungicide	Inorganic sulfur		BBCH 30-65			
			x							<i>Bacillus</i>				BBCH 30-65			
			x							<i>Clonostachys rosea</i>				BBCH 30-65			
		Chemical tools	x	x	x					Pyraclostrobin	Synthetic fungicide	QoI outer membrane quinone inhibitors	From BBCH 20 to BBCH 69	2	(COMET® 250 EC) Dosage: 0.7-1 L/ha	High risk (11)	
			x	x	x					Azoxystrobin	Synthetic fungicide	QoI outer membrane quinone inhibitors	From BBCH 30 to BBCH 69	2	(MIRADOR SC) Dosage: 0.8-1 L/ha	High risk (11)	
			x	x	x					Difenoconazole	Synthetic fungicide	DMI - demethylation inhibitors - BEI Class I	From BBCH 39 to BBCH 69	2	(TIPTOR ULTRA) Dosage: 1 L/ha	Medium risk (3)	
			x	x	x					Tebuconazole	Synthetic fungicide	DMI - demethylation inhibitors - BEI Class I	From BBCH 30 to BBCH 49	2	(FOLICURE® WG) Dosage: 1 kg/ha	Medium risk (3)	
			x	x	x					Mefenfluoconazole	Synthetic fungicide	DMI - demethylation inhibitors - BEI Class I	From BBCH 20 to BBCH 69	2	(REVVCARE®) Dosage: 0.75-1.5 L/ha	Medium risk (3)	
			x	x	x					Metconazole	Synthetic fungicide	DMI - demethylation inhibitors - BEI Class I	From BBCH 20 to BBCH 69	2	(APTRELL®) Dosage: 1L/ha	Medium risk (3)	
			x	x	x					Prothioconazole	Synthetic fungicide	DMI - demethylation inhibitors - BEI Class I	From BBCH 30 to BBCH 69	2	(PROSARO®) Dosage: 1 L/ha	Medium risk (3)	
			x	x	x					Tetraconazole	Synthetic fungicide	DMI - demethylation inhibitors - BEI Class I	From BBCH 40 to BBCH 69	2	(EMERALD 40 EW) Dosage: 3 L/ha	Medium risk (3)	
			x	x	x					Bromuconazole	Synthetic fungicide	DMI - demethylation inhibitors - BEI Class I	From BBCH 30 to BBCH 69	2	(NINEVI®) Dosage: 1 L/ha	Medium risk (3)	
			x	x	x					Benzovindiflupyr	Synthetic fungicide	SDHI - Succinate Dehydrogenase Inhibitors	From BBCH 30 to BBCH 69	1	(ELATUS® ERA) Dosage: 0.75-1 L/ha	Medium to high risk (7)	
			x	x	x					Bixafen	Synthetic fungicide	SDHI - Succinate Dehydrogenase Inhibitors	From BBCH 30 to BBCH 50	2	(ASCRA® XPRO) Dosage: 1.2-1.5 L/ha	Medium to high risk (7)	
x	x		x					Fluxapyroxad	Synthetic fungicide	SDHI - Succinate Dehydrogenase Inhibitors	From BBCH 25 to BBCH 69	2	(PRIAXOR®) Dosage: 1-1.5 L/ha	Medium to high risk (7)			
								Fluopyram									
								Metconazole									
								Fenpropidin	Synthetic fungicide	Amines - IBE-Class II morpholines			1		(5)		
							tempicoxamid	Synthetic fungicide	QoI								
ADOPT-IPM solutions								Cultivar mixture	Genetic (resistant varieties, etc.)		From Sowing to Harvest (BBCH 90-91)		The mixture should be composed of 3-4 cultivars with varying level of resistance.				
								Holistic IPM approach in wheat-based cropping systems	A mix of cultural, genetic, and conservation biological control				The template is not fully adapted to describe the IPM solution, based on a large combination of options for landscape management (grass & flower strips, multispecific hedgerows to attract beneficial organisms) and cultural management (crop rotation, resistant cultivars, intercropping, sowing date, companion crops, moderate fertilisation, mechanical weeding), targeting all main weeds (blackgrass, ryegrass, Galium aparine, ...), diseases (septoria, rusts, ...) and invertebrate pests (aphids, slugs) in wheat-based cropping systems				
								MBCAs (<i>Bacillus</i> sp. x <i>Trichoderma</i> sp. Formulations)	Microbiological fungicide		From sowing to Flowering (BBCH 50-59)						

Wheat bunt (*Tilletia* sp.)

Crop	Insect pests and diseases	Management solutions	Country					Solution/Practice/Active ingredient	Product category	Chemical group	Production stage (if possible with reference to BBCH scale)	Max number of application per year	Application Details and Notes (commercial product example)	Resistance risk (FRAC code)	
			IT	FR	ES	BE	NL								DK
Wheat	Wheat bunt (<i>Tilletia</i> sp.)	Agronomic tools	x	x					wide crop rotations			Pre-season			
			x	x					bury previous crop residues			Pre-season			
			x	x					avoid sprinkler irrigation			From Sowing to Harvest			
		Genetic Tools													
		Monitoring													
		Physical methods													
		Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)	x							<i>Pseudomonas chlororaphis</i> (strain MA 342)	Microbiological fungicide		seed treatment		
		Chemical tools	x							fludioxonil	Synthetic fungicide	FRAC 12	seed treatment		
x								fluxapyroxad	Synthetic fungicide	SDHI - Succinate Dehydrogenase Inhibitors	seed treatment				
x								prothioconazole	Synthetic fungicide	DMI - demethylation inhibitors - BEI Class I	seed treatment				
x								triticonazole	Synthetic fungicide	DMI - demethylation inhibitors - BEI Class I	seed treatment				
ADOPT-IPM solutions															
								Holistic IPM approach in wheat-based cropping systems	A mix of cultural, genetic, and conservation biological control				The template is not fully adapted to describe the IPM solution, based on a large combination of options for landscape management (grass & flower strips, multispecific hedgerows to attract beneficial organisms) and cultural management (crop rotation, resistant cultivars, intercropping, sowing date, companion crops, moderate fertilisation, mechanical weeding), targeting all main weeds (blackgrass, ryegrass, Galium aparine, ...), diseases (septoria, rusts, ...) and invertebrate pests (aphids, slugs) in wheat-based cropping systems		

Leaf necrosis (*Alternaria* sp; *Cladosporium* sp; *Epicoccum* sp; others.)

Crop	Insect pests and diseases	Management solutions	Country					Solution/Practice/Active ingredient	Product category	Chemical group	Production stage (if possible with reference to BBCH scale)	Max number of application per year	Application Details and Notes (commercial product example)	Resistance risk (FRAC code)		
			IT	FR	ES	BE	NL								DK	CN
Wheat	Leaf necrosis (<i>Alternaria</i> sp; <i>Cladosporium</i> sp; <i>Epicoccum</i> sp; others.)	Agronomic tools	x	x	x				wide crop rotations			Pre-season				
			x	x	x				bury previous crop			Pre-season				
			x	x	x				avoid sprinkler irrigation			From Sowing to Harvest				
		Genetic Tools														
			Monitoring													
		Physical methods														
			Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)	x						Sweet orange essential oil	Biological fungicide	Natural compound	From BBCH 50 to BBCH 69	4 per crop cycle	(PREV-AM® PLUS) Dosage: 2 L/ha	
				x						Sulfur	Biological fungicide	Inorganic	Start of treatments since there are favorable conditions for the	1	(Zolfo Flow MCT) Dosage: 3.5-4.5 L/ha	
		Chemical tools														
			ADOPT-IPM solutions		x					Holistic IPM approach in wheat-based cropping systems	A mix of cultural, genetic, and conservation biological control				The template is not fully adapted to describe the IPM solution, based on a large combination of options for landscape management (grass & flower strips, multispecific hedgerows to attract beneficial organisms) and cultural management (crop rotation, resistant cultivars, intercropping, sowing date, companion crops, moderate fertilisation, mechanical weeding), targeting all main weeds (blackgrass, ryegrass, Galium aparine, ...), diseases (spetoria, rusts,...) and invertebrate pests (aphids, slugs) in wheat-based cropping systems and enhancing natural enemies	
					x			Strip cropping (oats)								

Aphids

Crop	Insect pests and diseases	Management solutions	Country					Solution/Practice/Active ingredient	Product category	Chemical group	Production stage (if possible with reference to BBCH scale)	Max number of application per year	Application Details and Notes (commercial product example)	IRAC code			
			IT	FR	ES	BE	NL								DK	CN	
Aphids		Agronomic tools							Choose an early sowing time								
										Reduce amount of nitrogenous fertilizers.							
										Increase potassium fertilizer.							
		Genetic Tools								Choose tolerant plant varieties, such as Chinese wheat 175							
			Monitoring	x	x					Threshold: 80% of culms with aphids.							
		Physical methods		x	x					Before carrying out the treatment, evaluate the presence, the amount of the natural limiters and their potential capacity in containing the development of the phytophagous population							
										Radars and GPS, GIS, RS analyses are used to monitor and predict adult aphids. Also suction traps are used (Farmer can get information from plant protection station on wheat aphid flight);							
										Use yellow traps to capture adult aphids (2-3 traps per mu).							
		Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)								Search and count aphids weekly from wheat seeding growth to milk-ripe stage. Count on 15 plants each of 3 to 5 spots along "Z", walk through field.							
										Action threshold is 3 to 5 aphids per 10 plants on average.							
		Chemical tools								E-β-farnesene EBF alarm pheromone					Spray E-β-farnesene EBF alarm pheromone of aphids over field push out aphids and to attract natural enemies.		
										gramine –based natural products							
										Furanocoumarins –based natural products.							
										Aphidiidae wasps	Parasitoid					Place egg cards with beneficial Aphidiidae wasps (but then do not spray insecticides)	
										<i>Asaphes vulgaris</i>	Parasitoid					Release ladybird beetles (<i>Asaphes vulgaris</i>)	
		ADOPT-IPM solutions								Tau-fluvalinate	Synthetic insecticide	Pyrethroids and pyrethrins	Treat preventively or at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 30 days before harvest	2	(EVURE® PRO) Dosage: 0,2 l/ha	3A	
										Flonicamid	Synthetic insecticide	Chordotonal organ nicotinamidase inhibitors				2B	
										Pirimicarb	Synthetic insecticide	Carbamate					
										Deltamethrin	Synthetic insecticide	Pyrethroids and pyrethrins				3A	
										Acetamiprid	Synthetic insecticide	Neonicotinoids				4A	
										Acephate	Synthetic insecticide	Organophosphates				1B	
										Imidacloprid	Synthetic insecticide	Neonicotinoids				4A	
										Cypermethrin	Synthetic insecticide	Pyrethroids and pyrethrins				3A	
		ADOPT-IPM solutions								Flowerstrips	Cultural					aphidiphagous predators and	
										Intercropping	Cultural		Post-emergence (BBCH 09-19)			finding of herbivores as well as	
								Intercropping cornflower in wheat fields to enhance biological control	Cultural		Post-emergence (BBCH 09-19)			When planting wheat, the cornflower belt is planted at 20:1 in the wheat field			
								Silicon-based tools(plant resistance inducers)	Bioestimulant					The wheat is sprayed with silicon fertilizer after turning green			
								Holistic IPM approach in wheat-based cropping systems	A mix of cultural, genetic, and conservation biological control					The template is not fully adapted to describe the IPM solution, based on a large combination of options for landscape management (grass & flower strips, multispecific hedgerows to attract beneficial organisms) and cultural management (crop rotation, resistant cultivars, intercropping, sowing date, companion crops, moderate fertilisation, mechanical weeding), targeting all main weeds (blackgrass, ryegrass, Galium aparine, ...), diseases (spetoria, rusts,...) and invertebrate pests (aphids, slugs) in wheat-based cropping systems			
								Strip cropping (oats)	Cultural					plant finding of herbivores and			

Weeds

Crop	Management solutions	Production stage	Weeds	Country						Solution/Practice/Active ingredient	NOTE											
				IT	FR	ES	BE	NL	DK			CN										
Wheat	Agronomic tools					x					wide crop rotations											
		Physical methods										mechanical weeding										
	Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)																					
	ADOPT-IPM solutions																					
			Ambrosia artemisiifolia										combination of options for landscape management (grass & flower strips, multispecific Biocontrol agent. Predator of the weed A. artemisiifolia)									
	Chemical tools	Pre-sowing	Gramineae and Dicotyledons	x	x	x							Glyphosate	Company limit on the use of glyphosate on non-tree crops. Each company for a single year (1 January 31 December) can have a maximum quantity of Glyphosate (reference to formulations 360 g/L) equal to 2 L for each hectare of non-tree crops on which the use of the product is permitted. The total quantity of Glyphosate obtained from the calculation 2 L/ha x n. ha is the maximum available for use on all non-tree species grown in compliance with the formulation label.								
		Pre-emergence	Gramineae and Dicotyledons	x										Triallate (1)	Pre-emergence weeding of wheat and barley is permitted once every 2 years on the same plot. This practice is an alternative to early post-emergence weeding (1) graminicide							
				x	x	x									Flufenacet (2)	(2) Not usable on wheat and barley if used for pre-emergence weeding of the previous crop						
				x	x	x									Pendimethalin (2)	(3) dicotyledonicidal with secondary action on grasses						
				x	x	x									Prosulfocarb	(4) Dicotyledonicidal						
				x	x	x									Diflufenican (3)	(5) usable maximum once every 2 years on the same plot regardless of the crop on which it was applied						
		Early post-emergence	Gramineae and Dicotyledons	x	x	x									Bifenox (4) (5)	Early post-emergence weeding is an alternative to pre-emergence weeding (2) Not usable on wheat and barley if used for pre-emergence weeding of the previous crop						
				x	x	x									Diflufenican (3)	(3) dicotyledonicidal with secondary action on grasses						
				x	x	x									Prosulfocarb	(4) dicotyledonicidal						
				x	x	x									Beflubutamid	(5) usable maximum once every 2 years on the same plot regardless of the crop on which it was applied						
				x	x	x																
		Post emergency	Gramineae		x	x	x									Fenoxaprop-p-ethyl (6)	(6) Not effective on Lolium					
					x	x	x										Pinoxaden	(7) Not permitted on barley				
					x	x	x											Diclofop-methyl				
					x	x	x												Clofinafop(7)			
					x	x	x													Amidosulfuron		
			Dicotyledons			x	x	x											Metsulfuron methyl			
						x	x	x													Tribenuron-methyl	
						x	x	x													Mecoprop-P	
	x					x	x														Dichlorprop-p	
	x					x	x														Florasulam	
	x					x	x															Amidosulfuron
Gramineae and Dicotyledons				x	x	x													2,4-D			
				x	x	x														MCPA		
			x	x	x															Clopyralid		
			x	x	x																Halauxifen-methyl	
			x	x	x																Iodosulfuron methyl sodium	
			x	x	x																Thiencarbazone (7)	
			x	x	x																Bensulfuron	
			x	x	x															Mesosulfuron-methyl (7)		
			x	x	x																Propoxycarbazone-sodium (7)	
			x	x	x																	Diflufenican (3)(8)
			x	x	x															Pyroxulam (7)		

Examples of IPM Packages on wheat

Example n°1 - China

Pests (pathogen, insect, weed...)	Baseline (Farmer's strategy/control)	ADOPT-IPM strategy
Wheat aphid (<i>Rhopalosiphum padi</i> and <i>Sitobion avenae</i>)	Monitoring (observation: presence) + chemical (imidacloprid)	Monitoring + cornflower Intercropping + Chemical (imidacloprid) reduced usage by 35-50%
Wheat aphid (<i>Rhopalosiphum padi</i> and <i>Sitobion avenae</i>)	Monitoring (observation: presence) + chemical (imidacloprid)	Monitoring + 2g/L silicon + Chemical (imidacloprid) reduced usage by 50%
Common ragweed (<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>)	Monitoring (observation: presence) + chemical (Aminopyralid)	<i>Ophraella communa</i> produced by CAAS + chemical (Aminopyralid)

Example n°2 - Belgium

Pests (pathogen, insect, weed...)	Baseline (Farmer's strategy/control)	ADOPT-IPM strategy
<i>Fusarium</i> sp.	Chemical (various conventional and organic PPP possibly used, Serenade was used as positive treatment in organic prod.)	Monitoring (symptom scoring) + application of various formulations (Bacillus x trichoderma x nitrate, Bacillus x Trichoderma, lipopeptides)
<i>Zymoseptoria</i> sp.	Chemical (various conventional and organic PPP possibly used, Serenade was used as positive treatment in organic prod.)	Monitoring (symptom scoring) + application of various formulations (Bacillus x trichoderma x nitrate, Bacillus x Trichoderma, lipopeptides)
Aphids	Chemical (various conventional and organic PPP possibly used)	Entomofauna monitoring + application of various formulations (Bacillus x trichoderma x nitrate, Bacillus x Trichoderma, lipopeptides)

MAIZE

The maize IPM package is shown on the following pages. Each sheet is related to a different pest (pathogen, insect, weed), with the corresponding management solutions.

Spodoptera frugiperda

Crop	Insect pests and diseases	Management solutions	Country							Solution/Practice/Active ingredient	Product category	Chemical group	Production stage (if possible with reference to BBCH scale)	Max number of application per year	Application Details and Notes (commercial product example)	IRAC code	
			IT	FR	ES	BE	NL	DK	CN								
Maize	<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>	Agronomic tools															
		Genetic Tools															
		Monitoring															
		Physical methods															
		Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)															
		Chemical tools															
										Push-pull with semiochemicals and intercropping systems controlling fall armyworm	Physical (pest exclusion, etc.)		From Post-emergence (BBCH 10-19) to Fruit development (BCH 71-89)		we will make an application instruction for Push-Pull strategy to control the FAW in maize, (From IPPAS-AAAS)		
										Chelonus formosanus	Biocontrol agent		From Post-emergence (BBCH 10-19) to Flowering (BCH 51-59)		Mix-releasing with Trichogramma. Hanging the releaser in the middle leaf. do not release in rainy days		
										active in China	Monitoring						
										new-generation biosensors	Monitoring				detection of the natural pheromone by odorant proteins from the targeted species		
										push-pull practice with synthetic volatiles	Physical (pest exclusion, etc.)				combination of synthetic repellents and attractants		
										push-pull practice with plants	Physical (pest exclusion, etc.)		From Pre-emergence (BBCH 10-19) to Fruit development (BCH 71-89)		combination of repellent and attractant plants		
										Telenomus remus reared on Spodoptera litura	Biocontrol agent		From Pre-emergence (BBCH 10-19) Stem elongation (BBCH 30-39)		release of 200 Telenomus wasps/667m2, 7 days later, release of 200 Telenomus wasps again		
										Metarhizium rileyi granules for the control of Spodoptera frugiperda and its synergistic effects with chemical pesticide,	Biocontrol agent		From Pre-emergence (BBCH 10-19) to Flowering (BBCH 51-59)		release of 1 kg Metarhizium rileyi granules/667m2		
										control maize Spodoptera	Biological insecticide						
								pheromone traps	Monitoring								

Ostrinia nubilalis

Crop	Insect pests and diseases	Management solutions	Country							Solution/Practice/Active ingredient	Product category	Chemical group	Production stage (if possible with reference to BBCH scale)	Max number of application per year	Application Details and Notes (commercial product example)	IRAC code	
			IT	FR	ES	BE	NL	DK	CN								
Maize	<i>Ostrinia nubilalis</i>	Agronomic tools	x	x						Defibration of stalks and timely plowing.			Pre-season				
		Genetic Tools															
		Monitoring	x	x	x					Threshold: only in case of confirmed presence on the II and III generation.							
		Physical methods	x	x													
		Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)	x							Trichogramma brassicae	Parasitoid						
			x							Bacillus thuringiensis Subsp. Kurstaki	Microbiological insecticide						
			x							Bacillus thuringiensis Subsp. Aizawai	Microbiological insecticide						
		Chemical tools															
										Spinosad	Biological insecticide	Spinosyns	Treat preventively or at the first appearance of parasites. Suspend treatments 90 days before harvest	1 (Only in pre-flowering)	(LASER) Dosage: 200 ml/ha	5	
										Trichogramma ostrinae reared on Eri silkworm eggs	Biological insecticide		From Stem elongation (BBCH 30-39) to Flowering (BBCH 51-59)		(Against Ostrinia furnacalis) release of 5000 Trichogramma ostrinae wasps/667m2, 7 days later, release of 5000 Trichogramma again		

Helicoverpa armigera

Crop	Insect pests and diseases	Management solutions	Country							Solution/Practice/Active ingredient	Product category	Chemical group	Production stage (if possible with reference to BBCH scale)	Max number of application per year	Application Details and Notes (commercial product example)	IRAC code	
			IT	FR	ES	BE	NL	DK	CN								
Maize	<i>Helicoverpa armigera</i>	Agronomic tools							x	Optimize the habitat diversity and composition surrounding the focal maize field, or plant functional plants within or adjacent the maize field	Ecological mediation		Pre-season				
										x	Reduce chemical fertilizer (N/P/K) inputs to conserve natural enemies and suppress the polyphagous pests	Agricultural management		During the season			
		Genetic Tools															
		Monitoring								x	Threshold: widespread presence of initial attacks.						
		Physical methods															
		Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)									x	<i>Hippodamia variegata</i>	Generalist predator		During the whole season		
											x	<i>Trichogramma chilonis</i>	Egg parasitoid		2-3 days before the female adult oviposition		
		Chemical tools															
		ADOPT-IPM solutions								x	Ecological mediation of polyphagous pests (i.e., <i>Helicoverpa armigera</i>) in maize	cultivation management practice		From Stem elongation (BBCH 30-39) to Harvest (BBCH 30-39)		the nitrogen fertilizer applications followed the need of maize growth	

Weeds

Crop	Management solutions	Production stage	Weeds	Country						Solution/Practice/Active ingredient	NOTE			
				IT	FR	ES	BE	NL	DK			CN		
Maize	Agronomic tools					x					wide crop rotations			
	Physical methods						x					mechanical weeding		
	Biological tools (substances allowed in organic farming)													
	ADOPT-IPM solutions	From Post-emergence (BBCH 10-19) to Post-harvest	Ambrosia artemisiifolia		x						x	Large mass rearing system of <i>Ophraella communa</i>	Not usable in France until authorization by government. Caution with combination with other IPM tools such as chemical pesticides or biopesticides. Need several months without disturbances (no tillage). Eggs and larvae can be predated by ladybugs. China: Release 150-450 <i>Ophraella communa</i> per hectare to control ragweed about 20 cm tall	
	Chemical tools	Pre-sowing	Gramineae and Dicotyledons		x	x	x					Glyphosate (1)	(1) Company limit on the use of glyphosate on non-tree crops.	
		Pre-emergency	Gramineae and Dicotyledons		x		x						Terbuthylazine (2)(3)(4)(5)	Pay attention to the development of resistant weeds.
					x	x	x						Pendimethalin	Localized treatments are recommended (in fact for Alternatively, open-field interventions can be made on 50% of the company's surface area planted with corn. On the rest interventions only in post emergency.
					x	x	x						Isoxaflutole (6)	(2) In one year a maximum of 750 g/ha of Terbuthylazine sa.
					x		x						Thiencarbazone-methyl (7)	(3) Can only be used in pre emergency or early post emergency or post emergency.
					x	x	x						Pethoxamid	(4) Can be used locally on the sowing row or on a maximum of 50% of the surface cultivated with corn.
					x	x							Aclonifen (8)	(5) Can be used only once every 3 years on the same plot.
					x	x	x						Clomazone	(6) Can only be used in pre or post emergencies. Treatments allowed only in companies that have detected the presence of Abutilon in previous years.
				x								Flufenacet	(7) Maximum 1 treatment per year.	
				x	x	x						Dimethenamid-P	(8) Can be used locally on the sowing row or on 50% of the corn surface. Or it can be used max once every 2 years on the same plot regardless of whether it is applied on sugar beet, corn, sorghum, tomato, sunflower, soybean.	
				x	x	x						Mesotrione	(9) Can be used locally on the sowing row or on 50% of the corn surface. Or it can be used max once every 2 years on the same plot regardless of whether it is applied on sugar beet, corn, sorghum, tomato, sunflower, soybean.	
		x	x	x						Sulcotrione	(10) Only 1 application allowed every 3 years on the same plot.			
Early post emergency		Gramineae and Dicotyledons		x		x						Terbuthylazine (2)(3)(4)(5)	(2) In one year a maximum of 750 g/ha of Terbuthylazine sa.	
				x	x	x						Pendimethalin	(3) Can only be used in pre emergency or early post emergency or post emergency.	
				x	x	x						Isoxaflutole (6)	(4) Can be used locally on the sowing row or on a maximum of 50% of the surface cultivated with corn.	
				x	x	x						Dimethenamid-P	(5) Can be used only once every 3 years on the same plot.	
				x		x						Thiencarbazone-methyl (7)	(6) Can only be used in pre or post emergencies. Treatments allowed only in companies that have detected the presence of Abutilon in previous years.	
			x								S-Metolachlor (9)	(7) Maximum 1 treatment per year.		
			x	x	x						Clomazone	(8) Can be used locally on the sowing row or on 50% of the corn surface. Or it can be used max once every 2 years on the same plot regardless of whether it is applied on sugar beet, corn, sorghum, tomato, sunflower, soybean.		
Post emergency	Gramineae and Dicotyledons		x	x	x						Rimsulfuron	(9) Can be used locally on the sowing row or on 50% of the corn surface. Or it can be used max once every 2 years on the same plot regardless of whether it is applied on sugar beet, corn, sorghum, tomato, sunflower, soybean.		
			x	x	x						Nicosulfuron	(2) In one year a maximum of 750 g/ha of Terbuthylazine sa.		
			x								Terbuthylazine (2)(3)(4)(5)	(3) Can only be used in pre emergency or early post emergency or post emergency.		
			x	x	x						Sulcotrione	(4) Can be used locally on the sowing row or on a maximum of 50% of the surface cultivated with corn.		
			x	x	x						Mesotrione	(5) Can be used only once every 3 years on the same plot.		
	Dicotyledons		x	x	x							Tembotrione		
			x	x	x							Foramsulfuron		
			x	x	x							Prosulfuron (10)	(10) Only 1 application allowed every 3 years on the same plot.	
			x	x	x							Thifensulfuron - methyl		
			x	x	x							Clopyralid		
Dicotyledons and Cyperaceae		x	x	x							Dicamba			
		x	x	x							Fluroxypyr			
Perennial dicotyledons		x	x	x							Florasulam			
		x	x	x							Pyridate			
		x		x							Halosulfuron methyl			
											Bentazone			
											MCPA (11)	(11) A maximum of 10% of the company area planted with corn.		

Examples of IPM Packages on maize

Example n°1 - China

Pests (pathogen, insect, weed...)	Baseline (Farmer's strategy/control)	ADOPT-IPM strategy
Asian corn borer (<i>Ostrinia furnacalis</i>)	Monitoring (observation: presence) + chemical (Chlorantraniliprole)	<i>Trichogramma denrolimi</i> and <i>T. ostrinae</i> produced by GZU
Fall armyworm (<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>)	Monitoring (observation: presence) + chemical (Spinetoram; Chlorantraniliprole)	sex pheromone traps of FAW produced by CAAS + <i>Telenomus remus</i> produced by GZU + Bt (G033A) produced by CAAS

Example n°2 - China

Pests (pathogen, insect, weed...)	Baseline (Farmer's strategy/control)	ADOPT-IPM strategy
maize pest (<i>Helicoverpa armigera</i>)	Monitoring (observation: presence) + chemical insecticide	Monitoring + remove potential host habitat + nitrogen fertilizer reduced

Example n°3 - China

Pests (pathogen, insect, weed...)	Baseline (Farmer's strategy/control)	ADOPT-IPM strategy
Common ragweed (<i>Ambrosia artemisiifolia</i>)	Monitoring (observation: presence) + chemical (Aminopyralid)	<i>Ophraella communa</i> produced by CAAS + chemical (Aminopyralid)
maize Spodoptera <i>frugiperda</i>	chemical pesticide	Bt G033A 1000g micro-granule per mu
maize pest (<i>Helicoverpa armigera</i>)	Monitoring (observation: presence) + chemical insecticide	Monitoring + remove potential host habitat + nitrogen fertilizer reduced

4. Conclusion

We would like to remind you that the IPM packages remain constantly updated throughout the ADOPT-IPM project period, according to the innovative solutions that are evaluated and developed. The final step will be to make this information public through the dedicated website.

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